

Gustav Klimt's Portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*: Colonial Encounters, Artistic Patronage, and Provenance History (1897–2025)

Gustav Klimt,
Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona, 1897
 Oil on canvas, 65.5 x 54 cm
 Private Collection

ETHNOLOGICAL EXHIBITIONS IN VIENNA

Ethnological exhibitions—known in the German-speaking world as *Völkerschauen*—were a form of commercial public presentation of people from different ethnic origins that gained popularity in Europe and North America during the 19th and early 20th centuries. These events, which featured individuals predominantly from colonized regions, were staged in zoological gardens, amusement fairs, museums, and international expositions. Although they must be critically examined from a contemporary perspective, *Völkerschauen* at the time combined elements of popular entertainment with an ostensibly educational agenda rooted in colonial and ethnographic worldviews. In Vienna, as in many other European metropolises, such spectacles were embedded in the fabric of popular culture and attracted wide audiences across social strata. Particularly noteworthy in the history of the *Völkerschauen* in Vienna were the presentations of the Ashanti, also known as Asante, a part of the Akan ethnic group, from what is now Ghana.

In order to adequately contextualize the visual and discursive conditions under which the 1896 and 1897 ethnographic exhibitions in Vienna unfolded (see below), it is essential to consider earlier forms of African representation within the cultur-

Fig. 1: Franz Wolf (lithograph) after a drawing by Johann Nepomuk Hoechle, *The Ashanti at the Academy of Fine Arts in Vienna*, ca. 1833
 Austrian National Library (ÖNB), Vienna

al and epistemic frameworks of the Habsburg Empire. The example of the Ashanti reveals that notions of African political power and cultural alterity had already entered the Viennese public sphere—and its visual regimes—well before the height of fin-de-siècle colonial spectacle. Although the Habsburg monarchy did not possess formal overseas colonies, its elite culture and scientific practices throughout the 19th century were nevertheless deeply embedded within colonial epistemologies and imaginaries. The Ashanti attracted considerable public interest in Vienna already in the first half of the 19th century. Contemporary newspapers reported in detail on the political organization, material wealth, and, above all, the military resistance of the Ashanti kingdom against British colonial expansion on the *Gold Coast*. These accounts shaped a perception of the Ashanti as both powerful and exotic—an ambivalent image that soon resonated in the visual arts.

Fig. 2: C. Millmann, *The King of the Ashanti and His Court*, 1873
 Illustriertes [sic!] Wiener Extrablatt, 18 August, 1873, front cover

Fig. 3: R. Lechner, *Arrival of the Ashanti troupe by ship at the Danube Canal in Vienna*, 10 July, 1896
Austrian National Library (ÖNB), Vienna

An early example is Johann Nepomuk Hoechle's (1790–1835) 1833 drawing of an Ashanti man, depicted in a dramatic, combative pose during a class at the Akademie der bildenden Künste in Vienna (Academy of Fine Arts Vienna) (fig. 1). The image not only testifies to the visibility of Africans in institutional contexts of the imperial capital, but also reveals how Black bodies were stylized and subjected to the visual grammar and pedagogical frameworks of European academic art. In the decades that followed, the figure of the Ashanti king recurred within Viennese visual culture—prominently on the 1873 front page of the *Illustriertes Wiener Extrablatt* (fig. 2), designed by C. Millmann on the occasion of the emperor's birthday, and in Wilhelm Gause's gouaches (see below) from 1897, which documented scenes from the "Ashanti Village" in the Prater.

These works—produced across diverse media and historical contexts—attest to a persistent European fascination with West African sovereignty and cultural "Otherness", mediated through the aesthetic and ideological frameworks of their time. Even Gustav Klimt, prior to his 1897 portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*, had depicted a Black figure in his 1885 ceiling painting *Allegory of Dance and Art* for the Stadttheater Fiume (today the "Croatian National Theatre Ivan pl. Zajc", Croatian: "Hrvatsko narodno kazalište Ivana pl.

Zajca" u Rijeci). From a contemporary perspective, such visual representations must be critically interrogated as part of a broader colonial visual regime: while granting visibility, they simultaneously constrained Black subjects within aestheticized and often exoticizing frameworks of alterity. A decolonial and interdisciplinary examination of these image practices remains a crucial yet still insufficiently explored area of research.

The Ashanti exhibitions drew massive crowds and widespread attention, illustrating both the immense popularity of such events and the complex, problematic relationships between Europe and its colonies at the end of the 19th century.

THE ASHANTI IN THE VIENNESE PRATER, 1896

After the notable success of the ethnological show organised by the private association *Wiener Thiergartengesellschaft* at the *Thiergarten am Schüttel*¹ in Vienna's Prater in 1895—with a group of just over 25 people from the Matabele tribe²—the zoo management,³ led by general secretary Victor Bamberger (Vienna, January 7, 1864 – Vienna, October 20, 1937) decided to recruit another "African tribe" for the following year.⁴ This time, they involved a group of around 70 Ashanti from West Africa, who had previously appeared at the 1896

Budapest Millennium Exhibition.⁵ There, approximately 250 West Africans—predominantly Ashanti—had been accommodated in the so-called “African Village”, an exhibit organized by the French impresario Ferdinand Gravier.⁶ Bamberger succeeded in bringing about 70 of these individuals—under what was effectively a paid “loan arrangement”—to Vienna for a nearly simultaneous presentation of what he called an *Aschanti-Dorf* (“Ashanti Village”).⁷ The Ashanti traveled by steamboat from Budapest to Vienna, arriving on 10 July, 1896 at the *Weißgerber* landing station on the *Donaukanal* (“Danube Canal”), where they were received by a large crowd of onlookers. There is evidence to suggest that not all members of the group arrived in Vienna at the same time. A photograph preserved in the *ÖNB Bildarchiv* (“Austrian National Library, Image Archive”) documents the group’s arrival aboard the paddle steamer *Greifenstein* (fig. 3).⁸ Contemporary newspapers, however, announce the Budapest postal steamer *Fiume* as the vessel in use.⁹

Between July and October 1896, the Ashanti lived in specially constructed huts and were instructed to perform their daily routines under staged and surveilled and closely supervised conditions, for the entertainment of the Viennese public.¹⁰ In addition to showcasing traditional activities, they performed dances and combat games.¹¹ This “Ashanti Village” attracted up to 6.000 spectators per day, transforming into a mass entertainment event.¹² The Austrian writer Peter Altenberg

(1859–1919) became a frequent visitor, and his 1897 prose sketches titled *Ashantee* contributed to the literary commodification and popularization of the exhibition.¹³ Even before Altenberg’s publication, the *Neues Wiener Tagblatt* declared that “Ashanti fever” had gripped Vienna, demonstrating the fervent exoticism and racialised curiosity that were at the heart of these events.¹⁴

Additionally, the *Neue Wiener Tagblatt* reported that, to mark the Emperor’s birthday on August 18, 1896, a further 25 Ashanti individuals were invited to Vienna.¹⁵ Near the original exhibition site, another of five huts were constructed to accommodate them. The expansion of the village underscored the event’s popularity and the organizers’ eagerness to capitalize on its success.¹⁶

As later sections of this text will demonstrate, Bamberger made little discernible effort to reflect the diverse ethnic identities of the West African individuals with whom he worked. Instead, he consistently employed the label “Ashanti”—a term that, by the late nineteenth century, had become deeply entrenched in the European imaginary as a symbol of colonial “Otherness”. This designation, popularized over decades through media and public discourse, served as a rhetorical shorthand that privileged recognizability over accuracy. It is plausible that this terminological continuity informed the conception of the “Ashanti Village” presented in Vienna in 1896.

Fig. 4: *Atelier Brand, Nāh-Badūh, 1896*
From the collection of Peter Altenberg, Wien Museum

A revealing passage in Peter Altenberg’s *Ashantee* underscores the slipperiness of these ethnographic labels.¹⁷ Altenberg gives the address of “Nāh-Badūh” (fig. 4), identified in the text as “Ashanti,” at “Lomo House” on “King’s Street” in “Christiansborg”—located in the very heart of Osu.¹⁸ In the same context, he mentions “Noë [Noah] Salomon Dowoonah [sic!],” who, despite the exhibition’s nomenclature, was not of “Ashanti” origin but a member of the Ga of Osu.¹⁹ Notably, Dowuona was in all likelihood related to the prince later portrayed by Gustav Klimt and Franz Matsch, further complicating the rigid categorizations imposed by the exhibition. What emerges is a pattern of generalized labeling and representational simplification, highlighting how ethnic nuance was often subordinated to the expectations of European spectatorship and the appeal of the “exotic” in fin-de-siècle Vienna.

THE 1897 GROUP: GA FROM OSU INSTEAD OF ASHANTI

Victor Bamberger, the resourceful secretary general of the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* (see Appendix A), temporarily rescued his business from financial ruin in 1896 due to the overwhelming success of the “Ashanti Village”. Capitalising on this achievement, Bamberger traveled to Accra in the winter of 1896/97 to *recruit*—or more accurately, to procure under unequal and colonial terms—a new group for further display. This endeavor was carried out with the formal approval and logistical support of the British colonial administra-

Fig. 5: *Christiansborg Castle (Osu Castle) in Accra, 1905*
The British Museum, London

tion.²⁰ From 1878 to 1957, the region was the *British Crown Colony of the Gold Coast*, part of *British West Africa*. At that time, Sir William Edward Maxwell (1846–1897) served as British Governor, with his seat at *Osu Castle* (“Fort Christiansborg”) (fig. 5) in Accra.

However, based on research conducted in Kumasi and Accra (Ghana) in 2012 and 2017, it became clear that Bamberger did not actually recruit Ashanti individuals for the Vienna exhibition, as widely claimed at the time, but rather members of the Ga community from Osu. Osu does not denote an ethnic group itself, but refers to a historically devel-

oped urban district in the coastal area of Accra. Its inhabitants are ethnically affiliated with the Ga-Dangme, one of the coastal groups in Ghana. Osu is marked by its own royal dynasty, a distinct cultural identity, and historically significant ties to European trade and missionary activity. The kings of Osu are called *Osu Mantse*.²¹ During the relevant period, this role was held by Nii [Gottfried] Alema Dowuona,²² who was married to Afiyee and reigned from 1887 until his death in July 1897²³—at a time when a group of his subjects was being exhibited in Vienna.²⁴ Bamberger was almost certainly in direct contact with the *Osu Mantse* while arranging participants for the “Ashanti Village”, a misnomer that both concealed the true origin of the individuals and enhanced colonial exoticisation.²⁵

Both negotiations with Osu leadership and the decision to send a larger group required the explicit approval of the *Osu Mantse*. As the heir to the Osu stool could not be spared due to his vital political and symbolic role, responsibility for the group fell to his cousin *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*,²⁶ who, together with his cousin Prince Nortey Ababio²⁷ and around 120 people from Osu, traveled to Vienna with Bamberger.²⁸ After a 53-day sea voyage on the mail steamer *Gertrud Woermann*²⁹ via Las Palmas to Hamburg, they reached Vienna on 17 April, 1897.³⁰ Despite being Ga from Osu, the group was presented to the public under the title *Die Goldküste und ihre Bewohner – Aschanti* (“The Gold Coast and its Inhabitants – Ashanti”). Their six-month “guest perfor-

Wiener Thiergarten 1897.
Die Goldküste und ihre Bewohner (Aschanti). — Häuptling und Vice-Häuptling.

Fig. 6: *Wiener Thiergarten 1897. The Gold Coast and its Inhabitants (Ashanti). – Chief and Vice Chief.*
Herbert Gröger, Vienna

Fig. 7: Gustav Klimt, *Prinz William Nii Nortey Dowuona*, 1897
Private ownership

mance” at the *Thiergarten* (until October 25) drew tremendously large crowds—up to 10,000 spectators per day.³¹ Contemporary newspapers reported breathlessly on the daily activities and staged scenes in the “Ashanti Village”, of-

ten sensationalizing even minor incidents.³² Members of the Viennese bourgeoisie invited the Ashanti to theatres and coffee houses and took them for visits to monuments and department stores.

In contrast to the earlier *Völkerschauen* presented by Carl Hagenbeck (1844–1913) in the Vienna *Rotunda* from 1878 onwards—where colonial subjects were displayed behind barriers to underline their “Otherness”—the Osu group in the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* was accessible to the public with almost no spatial separation.³³ Only their living quarters were off-limits. This spatial closeness intensified ethnographic voyeurism, giving spectators the illusion of intimacy while reinforcing colonial hierarchies through a spectacle of “authentic” African life, curated for European audiences.

AN ARTISTIC ENCOUNTER: GUSTAV KLIMT AND THE PRINCE OF OSU

As in the previous year, the so-called Ashanti also attracted considerable attention in 1897, and some achieved a degree of public celebrity. Among them were the schoolmaster Alfred Sappor, who later settled in Vienna,³⁴ and the head of the Osu community, *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*.³⁵ In accordance with royal tradition, it was the elder of the two cousins, William, who assumed leadership of the group during their time in Vienna. Numerous photographs exist of the cousins and their entourage in various situations at the *Thiergarten am Schüttel*, preserved in relevant archives and private collections.³⁶ One of the photographs depicts the two cousins standing side by side in front of a palanquin carried by members of the royal entourage (fig. 6). Above them, a parasol is held aloft—an important symbol of authority among both the Ga and the Asante. In both cultures, the parasol signifies the social rank and political power of its bearer; it functions as a visual emblem of dignity, protection, and elevated status, particularly during public appearances by chiefs or kings. The parasol is crowned with a bush baby (*Galago*)—the heraldic animal of Osu—serving as a symbolic marker of local identity and dynastic affiliation.³⁷ As my research has shown,³⁸ *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* was portrayed by both Gustav Klimt (Baumgarten, 14 July, 1862 – Vienna, 6 February, 1918) (fig. 7) and Franz Matsch (Vienna, 16 September, 1861 – Vienna, 5 October, 1942)³⁹ (fig. 11) that year, presumably during a single sitting. Klimt painted the West African prince in profile, while Matsch depicted him almost frontally.⁴⁰ This dual representation is consistent with other instances where Klimt and Matsch painted the same subject simultaneously, each from their own perspective. These joint sittings often resulted in subtle but notable variations in perspective.⁴¹ As will be discussed below, it is likely that Nikolaus Dumba (1830–1900)—the prominent Viennese industrialist, cultural patron, and supporter of both artists—commissioned the works.

Valuable insights into the *Gedächtnisausstellung Gustav Klimt* (“Gustav Klimt Memorial Exhibition”), organized by the art dealer Gustav Nebehay (1881–1935) in Vienna between February 6 and March 5, 1919, can be gleaned from an article by Richard Hoisel, editor of the *Wiener Woche*.⁴² This report contains not only the earliest known reproduction of Klimt’s portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*

Fig. 8: *Wiener Woche: In Memory of Gustav Klimt*, 1919

na (fig. 8) but also important information about its provenance. Like many works in the exhibition, the portrait likely originated from Klimt’s immediate estate.⁴³ The reproduction in the article shows that at the time, the estate stamp created by Nebehay had not yet been applied to the painting. Nebehay had the stamp specially made for the 1919 memorial exhibition to mark works from the estate—especially unsigned items such as drawings.⁴⁴ Whether the portrait was sold during the exhibition remains unclear. The next documented reference to ownership and provenance appears in a catalogue from the Viennese auction house *Kende* in 1923 (see below), where the painting was shown again—this time bearing the estate stamp for the first time. However, detailed visual analysis reveals that the estate stamp on Klimt’s portrait was not printed but painted with blue oil paint.⁴⁵ While interventions by third parties in Klimt’s oeuvre are problematic from a provenance perspective, the presence of the estate stamp has contributed to the consistent attribution of the portrait to Gustav Klimt, ultimately ensuring its rediscovery and recognition in later years.

ARTISTIC STYLE AND CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF KLIMT’S PORTRAIT

Stylistically, Gustav Klimt’s portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* belongs to his early body of work and is relatively straightforward to date, primarily due to the distinctive floral motifs emerging behind the sitter. These

floral elements, which would later become a hallmark of Klimt's mature portraiture, signal a key stage in his evolving artistic language. Notably, a similar integration of natural motifs to frame and psychologize the subject can be observed in the portrait of *Sonja Knips* (1898) (fig. 9), where floral forms encircle the subject's head, imparting a subtle sense of interiority.⁴⁶ The visual logic of the Dowuona portrait foreshadows this development. It registers as an early instance of Klimt's integration of organic forms to elevate and more pronounced in subsequent works, such as the 1902 portrait of *Emilie Flöge* (fig. 10), where the motif assumes heightened significance. Within these compositional strategies, the ornamentation functions as an abstract expression of the complex, relational dynamic between painter and model. Thus, the portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* assumes a pivotal place within Klimt's oeuvre: it represents not only a technical and compositional transition, but also an advanced crystallization of the symbolic strategies that would come to define his mature style. This transitional phase in Klimt's art is particularly marked by a tension between the meticulously rendered, naturalistic figure—with the sitter's carefully modelled face and dignified presence—and the vibrant, almost expressionistic treatment of the background. The painterly quality of the surface echoes Klimt's contemporaneous oil sketches for his *Fakultätsbilder* ("faculty paintings"), specifically *Jurisprudenz* ("Jurisprudence") (1897–98),⁴⁷ *Medizin* ("Medicine") (1898),⁴⁸ and *Philosophie* ("Philosophy") (1898),⁴⁹ produced around the same period. Within this broader-artistic context, the Dowuona portrait stands as both a significant work of Klimt's early period and a noteworthy example of the emergence of Symbolism in latenineteenth-century art.

The portrait was painted just months after Klimt was elected president of the newly established Vienna *Secession*. The con-

Fig. 10: **Gustav Klimt**, *Emilie Flöge*, 1902
Wien Museum

Fig. 9: **Gustav Klimt**, *Sonja Knips*, 1898
Belvedere, Vienna

text of its creation is inseparable from the opening of the second "Ashanti exhibition" at the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* during the Viennese summer of 1897—a defining event in the city's cultural calendar. While this exhibition undeniably staged colonial "Otherness" in exoticizing terms, it simultaneously fostered new forms of interaction and proximity between Viennese visitors and the West African participants. Many such encounters transcended the boundaries of the exhibition, resulting, at times, in social and even personal connections. It was within this complex and charged environment that Klimt

and Matsch found the extraordinary opportunity to portray a sitter beyond the traditional circles of Viennese artistic or social life—specifically, the immediate presence of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* in Vienna. The resulting portraits—which two are extant—should be regarded not simply as commissioned works, but as artistic responses to a singular moment of cultural encounter, enabled by the structures of the colonial exhibition and subtly engaged in questioning and complicating them. Thus, the creation of these two portraits can ultimately be interpreted not just as the execution of a patron’s commission, but as an artistic negotiation with the novel conditions set by colonial exhibition practice.

THE IDENTITY OF THE SITTER: TRACING BACK TO ACCRA

In a personal interview conducted on 30 July, 2017 in Kumasi, both the Asantehene Otumfo Osei Tutu II (b. 1950), who has ruled the *Ashanti Kingdom* since 1999, and the Paramount Chief of Bompata, Nana Effah-Apenteng (b. 1945), confirmed unequivocally that the individual depicted in Klimt’s portrait was not of Ashanti origin but instead a member of the Ga community. The decisive factor in this assessment was the sitter’s attire, which, according to these authorities, is distinctively associated with traditional Ga dress and thus excludes any affiliation with Ashanti cultural sartorial forms.

Following this revelation, I consulted *Ga Mantse* Nii Tackie Obiie II in Accra—an acquaintance since 2012—to further investigate the historical presence of Ga individuals in Vienna in 1897. This conversation occurred during the production of the three-part television documentary *The Kings of Africa: Tradition and Awakening* (2018).⁵⁰ The *Ga Mantse* referred me to the then-*Osu Mantse*, Nii Okwei Kinka Dowuona VI (1963–2021), who, in a brief conversation, confirmed that *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* was his ancestor. According to his account, the prince returned from Europe with gifts and souvenirs, and, crucially, had entered into a written contract delineating the terms of participation in the Vienna exhibition—an important document that, along with the objects, remains in the family’s possession.⁵¹

Subsequent fieldwork in Accra, undertaken in preparation for a television documentary on the history of the Klimt painting, enabled personal meetings with members of both royal family branches on 14 September 2024 as again on 17 and 18 April 2025.⁵² While a comprehensive examination of the preserved objects—most notably the aforementioned contract—was not yet feasible, there is a strong evidence to suggest that letters written by *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* during his time in Europe, sent to family in Accra, still exist. The preliminary findings of this ongoing research are based on interviews with *Osu Mantse* Notse Nii Nortey Owuo IV⁵³ of the *House of Amantra (Owuo We)* and Samuel Solomon Dowuona, head of the *House of Kinkawe Dzaase (Dowuona We)* in Accra. Their oral histories have provided information about

familial and historical contexts that are largely absent from written archives. Further interviews are scheduled for autumn 2025, with the intention of deepening the historical contextualisation of these objects and illuminating the broader legacy of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*.⁵⁴

In both Klimt’s and Matsch’s portraits, *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* appears in a strikingly elegant garment: a large white cotton cloth, interwoven with black geometric patterns, draped artfully over one shoulder and leaving the other bare. This mode of dress, still customary in the region today, signifies royal dignity and authority. It embodies a codified practice that signals social rank, cultivated restraint, and physical self-discipline. Contrary to previous assumptions equating the clothing with Ashanti Kente traditions, the textile clearly aligns with the ceremonial dress codes of the Ga community, which frequently feature white or black-and-white woven fabrics in ritual contexts. Within Ga symbolic systems, these colors signify purity, mental clarity, and a connection to the Atlantic Ocean—a central point of reference in the culture of Accra, the coastal city from which the Ga originate.

Photographic documentation from Vienna further substantiates this cultural attribution: in several images (see below), *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* is seen holding a flywhisk (*bodua*)—a traditional emblem of leadership. This symbol of authority features subtly in Klimt’s portrait as well, partially visible in the lower right corner of the canvas, intentionally included as an iconographic element. Within the royal iconography of the historic Ga-Dangbe chieftaincies, the flywhisk denotes affiliation with the ruling elite, and, in combination with the white-and-black garment, evokes potent connotations of sovereignty and spiritual power.

FROM THE “ETHNOGRAPHIC EXHIBITION” TO THE OSU STOOL?

Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona’s presence in Vienna is verifiably documented between 17 April and 25 October, 1897, as attested by contemporary reports and photographic evidence of his leadership of the Osu delegation. After the conclusion of the Vienna exhibition, part of the group continued to Hamburg and Stockholm, and it is highly probable that Dowuona accompanied them (for additional details, see Appendix A). In 1898, he is believed to have once again joined a delegation of approximately 90 West Africans who traveled at least to Berlin and Hamburg. By late summer of 1899, newspapers again referenced a *stattlicher Häuptling Nothei* (“stately chief Nothei”) in Vienna—a name that clearly alludes to *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*. Taken together, these sources imply that the prince remained in Europe, intermittently, from the spring of 1897 until the autumn of 1899 (see below).

Following the death of *Osu Mantse* Nii [Gottfried] Alema Dowuona in July 1897, the Osu stool passed to Noi Ababio, who was subsequently deposed in 1914.⁵⁵ The next docu-

mented *Osu Maŋtse* was William Nortey (Notei) Dowuona, whose reign extended from 1916 to 1931.⁵⁶ However, it has not yet been definitively confirmed whether this ruler was indeed the same individual that had been portrayed by Klimt and Matsch.

FRANZ MATSCH: A SECOND PORTRAIT OF THE PRINCE

The genesis of Gustav Klimt's portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* is inextricably linked to the parallel painting by Franz Matsch, with both works existing in a visual and historical dialogue that merits close comparative attention. Produced within the same period, these two portraits reveal divergent artistic intentions that reflect a broader aesthetic and ideological rift between the artists. Klimt was elected president of the Vienna *Secession* on 3 April, 1897—a milestone that underscores his increasing departure from academic conventions—whereas Matsch remained firmly aligned with the historicist approach. The artistic disagreements that arose over the commission for the faculty paintings ultimately led to their professional separation; nevertheless, in the case of the Dowuona portrait, the two artists once again worked, if not collaboratively, then concurrently and with mutual awareness of each other's work.

The portrait by Matsch was first documented by the Viennese art historian and art dealer Herbert Giese in his dissertation *Franz v. Matsch — Leben und Werk* (1976), where it

was misleadingly titled *Nubier mit Umhangtuch* (“Nubian with Cloak”).⁵⁷ Matsch's depiction of the Osu prince adopts an almost en face orientation, in deliberate contrast to Klimt's more introspective profile view. Particularly notable is the portrait's elaborately crafted frame, made from bamboo segments: to retain the rounded “node-like” appearance of the bamboo poles, they were cut at the root ball and joined with precise craftsmanship. The entire structure was painted a uniform color, which amplified the portrait's exoticizing visual effect. The choice of bamboo—an imported, colonial material—may itself be interpreted as embedding the subject within a consciously stylised, exotic spectacle.⁵⁸

NIKOLAUS DUMBA AS A POSSIBLE PATRON AND SUPPORTER

The Viennese industrialist and art patron Nikolaus Dumba (1830–1900) was the earliest known owner of Franz Matsch's portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*.⁵⁹ This fact makes it plausible that Dumba not only acquired the work but may indeed have commissioned it—potentially along with Klimt's portrait as well. This hypothesis is supported by a confluence of evidence highlighting Dumba's close personal and professional relationship with both artists, each of whom he considered among his most valued protégés. As early as 1893, Dumba commissioned Klimt to decorate the music salon of his palatial residence on Vienna's Ringstrasse, while he entrusted the dining room's decoration to Matsch. Dumba continued to support both artists. In 1897/98 and again in 1898/99, based on sketches from 1895⁶⁰ and 1896,⁶¹ he commissioned Klimt to execute the celebrated overdoor panels *Music* (“*Music*”) ⁶² and *Schubert am Klavier* (“*Schubert at the Piano*”),⁶³ works regarded as among Klimt's most important works prior to the dissolution of the *Künstler-Compagnie*.⁶⁴

Dumba's sustained interest in non-European art and cultures further substantiates this interpretation. As a co-founder and patron of the *k.k. Orientalisches Museum* (“Imperial and Royal Oriental Museum”, later the “MAK – Museum of Applied Arts”), he played a significant role in promoting cross-cultural collecting and display in Vienna from the 1870s onward. The decision to commission the portrait of an African dignitary would have suited both his collecting practices and the cosmopolitan self-styling that typified Vienna's liberal intellectual and artistic elite at the fin de siècle. In this context, the portrayal of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* can be seen as simultaneously an expression of enlightened patronage and an artefact of Vienna's deep entanglement with the colonial modernity of late-nineteenth-century Europe.

The practice of commissioning multiple portraits of the same subject was also consistent with the working methods of the *Künstler-Compagnie*. It was not uncommon for several artists to produce variations on a theme, allowing the patron to select the version that best matched their expectations. The

Fig. 11: Franz Matsch, *Prinz William Nii Nortey Dowuona*, 1897 Musée National d'Histoire et d'Art (MNAHA), Luxembourg

fact, that the elaborately framed and signed portrait by Matsch came into Dumba's possession—while Klimt's unsigned painting remained unframed—suggests that Matsch's version aligned more closely with the patron's taste and aspiration. Accordingly, it is plausible that Matsch received the definitive commission, with Klimt's painting remaining unsold.

PROVENANCE OF THE MATSCH PAINTING

With the acquisition of Franz Matsch's portrait, Dumba evidently obtained the version he deemed most satisfactory. After his death on 23 March, 1900, however, the painting's whereabouts remained untraced for decades.⁶⁵ Its provenance resurfaced in 1972, when it appeared at the *Dorotheum* auction (June 20, 1972; lot 82), where it was publicly illustrated for the first time and acquired by Viennese gallerist Kurt Kalb (1935–2022) of *Galerie Grünangergasse*.⁶⁶ The New York art dealer Robert Kashey (*Shepherd Gallery*) later stated that Kalb had sold him the portrait in the early 1970s.⁶⁷ Kalb maintained the portrait originated from Dumba's collection.⁶⁸ Kashey in turn sold the portrait to New York collector Winthrop Kellogg "Kelly" Edey (1938–1999). After an unsuccessful sale at *Sotheby's* New York on 13 October, 2020 (Lot 22), the work was eventually acquired by the *Musée National d'Histoire et d'Art (MNHA)* in Luxembourg in the *Sotheby's* online auction of 25 October, 2021 (Lot 511).⁶⁹

If the Matsch portrait indeed originated from the Dumba collection, the provenance is complicated by the fact that it is not explicitly listed among Dumba's surviving estate documents.⁷⁰ Dumba, renowned for his careful testamentary planning, specifically bequeathed selected artworks to designated associates and issued detailed provisions for the *Makart-Zimmer* ("Makart Room"). The rest of his extensive art collection—listed in the estate inventory in bulk, without individual identifications—was inherited by his daughter Irene Dumba (1864–1920), his universal heir. Upon her death, her heirs sold off much of the collection, possibly including the painting of Matsch.

Another possible provenance route is suggested by the recollections of Maria Polsterer-Kattus, daughter of Johann Kattus (d. 1972), who remembered seeing the portrait of the Osu prince in her youth at the *Villa Matsch* on Haubenbiglstraße in Vienna.⁷¹ At that time, the residence was home, among others, to the two daughters of Franz Matsch and his wife Therese Anna Kattus-Matsch (1868–1939), namely Theresia (1896–1991) and Hildegard Matsch (1897–1985). This testimony supports the hypothesis that the painting may have entered the Matsch family's possession by the 1920s and aligns with the provenance listed for the 1972 *Dorotheum* auction, where Hildegard Matsch is recorded as the consignor.⁷²

Whether the painting remained with Franz Matsch from the outset or, as is more likely, was commissioned and acquired

by Dumba and passed to the Matsch family only after Irene Dumba's death remains unresolved. Additional circumstantial evidence is provided by the recollection that Josef Kattus (1907–1990), Maria Polsterer-Kattus's uncle, acquired several works by Franz Matsch in later life, including a painted marble fountain originally from Nikolaus Dumba's Ringstrasse palace. Such objects suggest that transfers between the Dumba and Matsch/Kattus families may have taken place by way of inheritance or private acquisition and remain difficult to document with certainty.

THE KLIMT PAINTING: HISTORY AND LOSS

The painting by Gustav Klimt—almost certainly originating from the artist's estate (see above)—was first offered for sale on 4 May, 1923 as lot 53 at the S. [Samuel] *Kende* auction house in Vienna. The auction catalogue described it as a *Bildnis eines Negers, im Dreiviertelprofil nach rechts, um die Schultern ein weißer Mantel. Im Hintergrund exotische Pflanzen* ("Portrait of a Negro, in three-quarter profile facing right, with a white coat around his shoulders. Exotic plants in the background").⁷³ The lot was listed as painted on canvas, bearing an estate stamp, with dimensions of 65 by 53 cm and a starting price of 15,000 crowns. Some copies of the auction catalogue included a photographic reproduction of the portrait.⁷⁴ It is most likely that the work was acquired at this auction, or shortly thereafter, by Ernestine (Tina) Werner (Vienna, 24 February, 1887 – Vienna, 9 April, 1973), later Ernestine Klein.⁷⁵ A potential intermediary in this acquisition could have been Dr. Robert Eigenberger (1890–1979).⁷⁶ Beginning in 1922, he served as director of the *Gemäldegalerie* ("Paintings Gallery") at the *Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien* "Academy of Fine Arts in Vienna" and, as evidenced by a letter from 1938 (see below), advised the Klein family on matters of art. Edith Crossman (née Werner, Vienna, 6 February, 1908 – London, 16 June, 2000), Ernestine's daughter, from her first marriage, later stated in an interview with Robert Streibel that the family had "received" the Klimt painting via Eigenberger's involvement;⁷⁷ either through his recommendation at a *Dorotheum* auction or through his mediation shortly thereafter.⁷⁸ The acquisition aligns with the family's broader cultural engagement: Ernestine, whose first husband Hugo Werner (1882–1911) had died in 1911,⁷⁹ purchased Klimt's last studio at Feldmühlgasse 11 in Vienna on 29 December 1922, subsequently renovating it into a residence for herself, her daughter Edith, and her partner Felix Klein (Vienna, 11 April, 1887 – Baden, 27. February, 1974),⁸⁰ a wine wholesaler whom she met at Semmering—a mountain resort town in Austria, famous for its 19th-century villas, alpine scenery, and the nearby Semmering Railway—and married in 1926.⁸¹

The painting was lent in 1928 to the Vienna *Secession*. For the tenth anniversary of Klimt's death, it was shown at the *Klimt-Gedächtnisausstellung* ("Klimt Memorial Exhibition") from 27 June to 31 July, 1928. On 6 August, a few days after the exhibition's close, Ernestine Klein confirmed in writing she had re-

ceived the painting *Negerkopf* (“Negro Head”) back in perfect condition. The receipt is archived at the *Künstlerhaus*, Vienna, and refers explicitly to the exhibition catalogue and catalogue number.⁸² There, the painting was listed as number 10, from private ownership. According to Edith Crossman’s recollections, the painting later hung in her mother’s boudoir at Feldmühl-gasse 11 in Vienna.⁸³ Some interior photographs from Edith Crossman’s estate are offering glimpses of the domestic setting.

Felix and Ernestine Klein came from wealthy, assimilated Jewish families and at the time held Czechoslovakian citizenship. Together with his brother Otto (Ober Kortelez, 1886 – Sydney, 1954), Felix managed the wine wholesaler *Klein & Brandl AG* at Pfadenhauergasse 2-6 in Vienna.⁸⁴ The company stemmed from their mother Louise (née Brandl, d. 1941) and included branches and properties in Vienna, Budapest⁸⁵ and Esztergom–Kenyérmező.⁸⁶ Felix and Otto were both directors and the main shareholders.⁸⁷

Following the annexation of Austria into the *Deutsches Reich* (“German Reich”) on 13 March, 1938, the Klein family fled Vienna the very next day, 14 March, taking only a few suitcases and their mother Louise.⁸⁸ They initially sought refuge in Bratislava,⁸⁹ believing that their Czechoslovak citizenship would offer protection. Their household furnishings, including artworks, remained behind.⁹⁰ Their housekeeper Marie, who had worked for the Klein family for many years, attempted to rescue some belongings, but this proved unsuccessful. In the wake of Nazi expropriation, nearly everything was lost.⁹¹

In Bratislava, Ernestine and Felix Klein soon realised that the reach of Nazi persecution extended beyond Austria, threatening their safety even in Czechoslovakia. They fled to Kenyérmező near Esztergom in Hungary⁹² (see below) and on 1 November, 1938, continued their escape via Yugoslavia and Italy to Paris, where they stayed until 12 February, 1939. They then travelled to Nice⁹³ and on 1 August, 1942 to Monte Carlo, where they stayed until 20 January 1953.⁹⁴ Though officially neutral and independent, Monaco functioned as a key business hub for the Nazi regime and was regarded as comparatively safe for Jews. The principality issued false identity papers to Jewish residents to protect them from deportation. Ernestine and Felix Klein tried to live with great caution, and in the last year of the war they reportedly stayed in a *safe-room*, underscoring the intensifying danger they faced.⁹⁵

Meanwhile, the assets of Felix’s brother Otto and his wife Julie Klein (Vienna 1893–1990 Sydney), including their villa at Hietzinger Hauptstraße 20, were aryanised by decree on 27 September, 1939.⁹⁶ The villa’s furnishing and art collection were confiscated between 17 and 19 April, 1939 at Vienna’s *Dorotheum*.⁹⁷ After the war, the villa and other properties (a building plot in Kierling near Klosterneuburg) were restituted in 1949.⁹⁸ In addition, the couple and their legal successors initiated several restitution proceedings for the seized art collection.⁹⁹ Subsequently, the *Belvedere* in Vienna¹⁰⁰ (2008), the *Wien Museum*¹⁰¹ (2016), and the *Stiftung Museum Kunstpalast*

in Düsseldorf¹⁰² (2021) restituted artworks to the heirs of Otto and Julie Klein.¹⁰³

After the rushed departure from Feldmühl-gasse 11, Ernestine Klein reported in a *List of Jewish assets* as of 27 April, 1938 (file number 23201) completed in Bratislava on 16 July, 1938 that she owned “silverware, porcelain, pictures, knick-knacks and other works of art”, with no precise valuation (“due to her absence” an “exact estimate [...] was impossible”).¹⁰⁴ The wording matches Julie Klein’s asset declaration. As in the case of Felix’s brother, it can also be assumed in this case that the entire furnishings of Feldmühl-gasse 11 were foreclosed at the *Dorotheum* in Vienna in 1939. The sculpture “*Badende (Bather)*” by Gustinus Ambrosi (1893–1975), carved from Carrara marble, provides an indication of a possible forced sale of the contents of Feldmühl-gasse 11. This sculpture was demonstrably owned by Edith Crossman¹⁰⁵ and, along with the typical inventory of a middle-class flat, was put up for forced sale on 26 May, 1939 at *Dorotheum* on behalf of the district court as lot no. 252.¹⁰⁶ Also listed was an as-yet-untraced large landscape by Hugo Darnaut (lot 247, 112 by 165 cm)—the painting may correspond to one mentioned later in correspondence.¹⁰⁷

Ernestine and Felix Klein never discovered the fate of the furnishings and the majority of the artworks left behind in their villa at Feldmühl-gasse after fleeing in 1938.¹⁰⁸ On 10 May, 1939, the villa at Feldmühl-gasse 11 was sold to Magdalena Emin.¹⁰⁹ She and her family lived there until shortly before it was restituted to Ernestine Klein in 1947 (see below). According to the very precise appraisal of the building dated 6 May, 1939, which is several pages long, it can be assumed that the building was empty at the time of the sale to Magdalena Emin.¹¹⁰ The proximity in time to the aforementioned forced auction on 26 May, 1939 is evident.

In 1943, *Klein & Brandl A.G.* was partly liquidated by the Nazis. The *Landesgericht Wien* (“Vienna Regional Court”) subsequently asserted claims for damages against the two brothers¹¹¹ and carried out executions on the tangible assets of Otto and Felix Klein located in Austria from this time until March 1945.¹¹² However, executions and confiscations are likely to have begun much earlier; for example, the *Neuigkeits-Welt-Blatt* reported on 5 October, 1938 about a lawsuit by the Credit-Anstalt-Wiener Bankverein against both brothers, already abroad at the time.

After the end of the Second World War, the *Restitutionskommission* (“Restitution Commission”) set up at the *Landesgericht für Zivilrechtssachen* (“Regional Court for Civil Matters”) decided on 22 April, 1947 to initiate restitution proceedings for the property at Feldmühl-gasse 11 in Vienna to Ernestine Klein. The proceedings were concluded on 18 December, 1947.¹¹³ Ernestine and Felix Klein moved from Monte Carlo to Sanremo (Italy) on 20 January, 1953.¹¹⁴ In 1954, Ernestine sold the so-called *Klimt Villa*¹¹⁵ to the Republic of Austria. The couple, who were French citizens at the time, eventually returned to Vienna and initially lived in a ho-

tel. With the proceeds from the property's sale, the couple bought an apartment at Kärntnerring 2a/12, overlooking the *Hotel Bristol* and the *Vienna State Opera House*.

Although no formal claim for the objects they had left at Feldmühlgasse 11 in 1938 is known, four of Felix Klein's paintings were transferred to Monaco in 1948.¹¹⁶ The transfer was carried out by Prof. Thomas Rollecsek (1890–1975), the then public administrator for *Klein & Brandl A.G. in Liquidation*, which was in the process of being dissolved. The export licence for the four paintings, issued by the *Bundesdenkmalamt* ("Federal Monuments Office") on April 22, 1948, was granted at a time that almost coincided with the conclusion of the company's liquidation and its continuation under the new name of *Klein & Brandl Aktiengesellschaft* on 16 July, 1948.¹¹⁷ Since Felix Klein, unlike his brother Otto, was no longer involved in the newly established company, it is reasonable to assume that the paintings in question were personal belongings from his former office at the company's headquarters at Pfadenhauergasse 4 in Vienna. They were probably returned to him in the course of the company's restructuring. The four paintings are as follows: *Self-Portrait* by Friedrich von Amerling; *Gentleman Reading in the Library* by Johann Hamza; *Poultry Farm* by Carl Jutz; and *Forest Landscape* by Hugo Darnaut.¹¹⁸

Ernestine Klein died in her flat in Vienna on 9 April, 1973. In her will dated 6 May, 1966,¹¹⁹ she named her daughter Edith Crossman, as sole heir. Felix Klein died on 27 February, 1974 at the *Hotel Esplanade* in Baden near Vienna. In his will dated 18 September, 1956,¹²⁰ he also named his stepdaughter, Edith Crossman, as universal heir in the event that he outlived his wife Ernestine. Neither will mention the seized works or furnishings of Feldmühlgasse 11 in Vienna suggesting the couple had likely abandoned hope for their recovery long before.

RECONSTRUCTION OF THE PROVENANCE AND MOVEMENT HISTORY OF THE PAINTING FROM 1938 ONWARDS

The Klimt painting *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* is the subject of a comprehensive blog post published on 22 March, 2025 by the art technologist Zsófia Végvári, who operates the *Festményvizsgáló Labor*, a painting examination laboratory in Budapest.¹²¹ In her blog post, Végvári provides a detailed and scientifically informed account of the technical examination of the artwork, which is available to me.¹²² Végvári's post proved to be incredibly important for my further research in Hungary: it served as a crucial catalyst, unlocking processes and new lines of inquiry that had previously remained completely stagnant and rigid. Without her thorough analysis and public documentation, avenues essential to tracing the painting's provenance and understanding its history would likely have remained closed to me. Unaware of this prior analysis, I contacted her on 19 April, 2025 to request further details regarding the painting's ownership and provenance in Hungary. This initiated an active email exchange, culminating in a

personal meeting in Budapest on 24 May, 2025, during which key aspects of the Hungarian provenance were discussed, thereby opening new and promising avenues of archival research in Hungary, the Czech Republic, and Austria.

Even prior to my meeting with Ms. Végvári on 24 May, 2025, I had already been alerted by *Source 1*¹²³ to the existence of documents relevant to the painting's provenance. Subsequently, *Source 2*¹²⁴ provided additional—though fragmentary—information derived from these same materials, indicating significant features of the painting's movement and custodianship history in Hungary. Two written disclosures from *Source 2* to me, dated 19 and 30 March, 2025, contained key details that opened new perspectives on this topic. On 19 March, 2025, I requested by email that *Source 2* grant me full access to the relevant documents. However, *Source 2* made it clear that they had a strong personal interest in acquiring the painting and made the release of materials contingent upon my assistance in facilitating such an acquisition. In an email dated 30 March, 2025, *Source 2* stated verbatim: "Accordingly, the complete and detailed provenance will only be disclosed following the confirmed acquisition, in order to avoid any potential misuse, misrepresentation, or unintended circulation of sensitive information." With this statement, *Source 2* emphasized their willingness to provide the full provenance—but only in the event that their acquisition was successful, despite the considerable value of the documentation.

Following extensive research in Hungary, I was ultimately granted access on 29 May, 2025 to view these documents (see below) in Budapest, through *Source 3*¹²⁵ who also insisted on anonymity. I was permitted to transcribe the documents in full. Furthermore, I received copies and scans made in 2006 of the documents. Notably, the eighth and, to date, last known letter—a letter from Dr. Ferencz Horn to Dr. Mihály Pál Simon, dated 8 October, 1963—was evidently unknown to *Source 1*. I have not seen the original letter myself; the only information available comes from a few details relayed by *Source 2*.

SUMMARIZED EXCERPTS FROM HISTORICAL CORRESPONDENCE DOCUMENTING THE PAINTING'S OWNERSHIP AND MOVEMENT (1938–1963)

Letter 1 (German), 23 August, 1938, Pöstyén (present-day: Piešťany, Slovakia), from Ernestine Klein to Dr. jur. Fedor Vest (fig. 12).

Ernestine Klein, writing from Pistyan on August 23, 1938, addresses Fedor Vest, enclosing her power of attorney. She asks him to initiate, as previously discussed with her Budapest lawyer, the transfer of her household furnishings to Prague or Geneva, and requests that this be accomplished as soon as possible—ideally by the end of September—even though the apartment (Prague) is currently rented until then. Due to her limited financial resources, she asks Vest to accept

Fig. 12: *Letter 1, 23 August, 1938 (Pöstyén),* from Ernestine Klein to Dr. jur. Fedor Vest in Budapest
Private ownership

a success-based fee, and suggests that both his fee and transport costs could, if necessary, be covered by selling some of the furnishings. She thanks him in advance for his support and closes with respectful regards.

Ernestine Klein also supplied a detailed list of artworks, which included:

- 1/ *Pastell-Porträt, zweite Hälfte 18. Jahrhundert, nach Dr. [Robert] Eigenberger aus nächster Nähe [Jean-Étienne] Liotards stammend*
- 2/ *Qualitativ hochstehendes Blumenstück des Altwieners [Anton] Hartinger*
- 3/ *Grosse Waldlandschaft von [Hugo] Darnaut*
- 4/ *Neger von [Gustav] Klimt, Paradesstück der letzten Klimtausstellung im Künstlerhaus*
- 5/ *Selbstbildnis [Friedrich von] Amerlings*
- 6/ *Zwei [Moritz] Daffinger-Miniaturen auf Elfenbein, eine signiert, von Dr. [Robert] Eigenberger expertisiert, früherer Besitz [Moritz von] Königswarter."*

("1/ Pastel portrait, second half of the 18th century, identified by Dr. [Robert] Eigenberger as being in close proximity to the work of [Jean-Étienne] Liotard

2/ High-quality floral still life by the Old Viennese painter [Anton] Hartinger

3/ Large forest landscape by [Hugo] Darnaut

4/ 'Negro' by [Gustav] Klimt, showpiece of the most recent Klimt exhibition at the Künstlerhaus

5/ Self-portrait by [Friedrich von] Amerling

6/ Two [Moritz] Daffinger miniatures on ivory, one signed,

authenticated by Dr. [Robert] Eigenberger, formerly owned by [Moritz von] Königswarter.")

According to current research, the Klimt painting in question was transferred to Budapest in the months following this letter, facilitated by Fedor Vest, who acted on behalf of the owner and held the painting in his custody.¹²⁶

Letter 2 (German), 30 July, 1939, Nice, Felix Klein to Dr. jur. Fedor Vest.

This letter replies to Vest's communication of 26 July, 1939, which discussed, among other matters, negotiations with the *Compagnie d'Assurances* (C.A.). Felix Klein expressed approval for the negotiation strategy to date, but advised against making unnecessary concessions to the opposing party.

In the section concerning artworks, Klein offered remarks on various paintings: a piece by Josef Danhauser, though artistically accomplished, would be hard to sell. A painting attributed to the Veronese school he dismissed as "practically a ruin." He was, however, positive about a painting attributed to [Jacopo] Bassano, stating that it was fully signed, technically flawless, and of significantly higher quality than the attributed name would suggest—regardless of expert opinion. Furthermore, Klein reminded Vest that he was still awaiting a response about silverware and other paintings from a known source previously mentioned.

Letter 3 (German), 19 August, 1939, London, [Arthur J. Duff] to Dr. jur. Fedor Vest.

This letter is not directly relevant to the Klimt painting's history. Arthur J. Duff, a close associate of Felix Klein and a board member of *Dr. Megyeri Landwirtschaftliche Industrie AG* (this company will hereinafter be referred to as *Dr. Megyeri AG* – see Appendix B)¹²⁷ in Kenyérmező, reported on a new regulation that placed Jewish-owned property in the Protectorate—including property in Znaim (present-day: Znojmo)—under state control. Previous legal arrangements for Felix Klein were thus retroactively validated but could now lead to higher purchase prices. Duff advised liquidation of the Kahler and Löw mortgages, which were hindering sales negotiations. Klein's Prague lawyer, Dr. Holub, had negotiated administrative fees with provisional authorities, with any unrecognized costs to be paid from Klein's private Prague assets.¹²⁸ Correspondence regarding an unresolved case in Znaim (in the *Reichsprotektorat Böhmen und Mähren* [Protectorate of Bohemia and Moravia], established by Nazi Germany in March 1939) was to be directed to Duff's brother-in-law in Switzerland.

Letter 4 (German), 4 September, 1947, Budapest, Dr. jur. Fedor Vest to Irene Endrédi.

This pivotal letter summarizes the circumstances of the retrieval, transfer, and safekeeping of three paintings from Fe-

lix Klein's estate, among them the work *Negerbüste* ("Negro Bust") by Gustav Klimt, a pastel portrait in the style of Liotard, and a small painting of a thistle.

Vest expressed his general willingness to return all three paintings—provided his costs for transport, storage, and restoration were reimbursed. He referred to prior contact with Otto Klein, who he believed was acting for Felix. Vest stressed that he had acted solely in the Klein family's interest, without investigating ownership status.

He gave a detailed account of his actions, including securing several artworks at Otto Klein's urgent request, and removing them from the "German Reich" (the Klimt was considered especially significant, both materially and ideologically). In addition to the Klimt, the group included the Liotard-style pastel. Viewing the artworks in the already-confiscated villa, Vest remarked that he especially liked the thistle painting, to which Otto replied that, while attractive, it had little value and Vest could keep it if he managed to smuggle it out along with the others.

Vest described the considerable risk taken to retrieve the three works from the confiscated villa—risk that could have led to imprisonment in a concentration camp. He initially stored them in Vienna,¹²⁹ but, having been banned from the city, arranged for their movement to Budapest via a Klein family representative. The works, poorly packed, suffered significant damage.¹³⁰ Vest paid for a specialist to restore them and covered all associated costs, keeping Otto Klein informed.

In the period preceding the *Schlacht um Budapest* ("Siege of Budapest") (29 December, 1944 to 13 February, 1945), Vest moved the works and his valuables to a rural area, having them immured to protect against looting and destruction. It is very likely that Vest brought the paintings and other valuables to Kenyérmező near Esztergom, hiding them in one of the many *Dr. Megyeri AG* properties.

Now Vest demanded full reimbursement of all documented expenses (transport, restoration, secure storage), while rejecting the lump-sum settlement Felix Klein had suggested, and insisting on a comprehensive response—with legal action threatened if denied. The return of the two paintings supposedly gifted to Vest was also made conditional on recognition of these claims.

These statements must be considered within the historical context of Hungary's postwar instability. By 1947, Hungary was transitioning from pluralism to a rigid socialist order, with private property under increasing ideological and administrative pressure. Restitution procedures were opaque, state intervention in private assets was widespread, and property rights were precarious. Vest's actions in relocating and physically immuring the artworks are thus significant, as both protection and a deliberate measure to evade state seizure.

The letter also mentions a previously unknown individual, "Mr. Klaus Bülow", described as the Klein family's trustee in charge of overseeing the safeguarded assets. No entry for a "Klaus Bülow" could be found in *Adolph Lehmann's General Address Directory for Vienna* in the relevant years, though "Erich (Erik) Klaus-Bülow" is verifiably listed as of 1942.¹³¹

Letter 5 (Hungarian), 19 October, 1956, Budapest, Dr. Ferencz Horn¹³² to Dr. jur. Fedor Vest.

Acting on behalf of Felix Klein, Horn sought to negotiate the return or repurchase of the Klimt painting *Negerkopf* ("Negro Head"). Klein offered to acquire the painting at a price to be determined by the *Szépművészeti Múzeum* ("Museum of Fine Arts") in Budapest, to be paid in foreign currency through the Hungarian National Bank. If the price set was unacceptable to Vest, a supplementary payment in cash or kind could be negotiated, so long as the transaction was formally processed through *Artex*,¹³³ the Hungarian state art export agency.

Horn emphasized that the past would not be revisited. He confirmed the painting was not listed in public registers and therefore remained private property under existing law. Should other artworks reappear, Klein was open to purchasing them as well.

Letter 6 (Hungarian), 18 July, 1963, Budapest, Dr. Mihály Pál Simon to Dr. Ferencz Horn.

This letter summarizes a failed mediation attempt with Fedor Vest. On Simon's behalf, Horn approached Vest to obtain information about certain paintings for Felix Klein. Vest categorically refused contact, citing a police complaint filed by Otto and Felix Klein just after the Second World War with the political police. The complaint contained not only accusations against Vest's conduct at *Dr. Megyeri AG* in Kenyérmező,¹³⁴ but also politically sensitive allegations that Vest claimed were knowingly untrue. Although the case was dropped, it left Vest with lasting mistrust. Even in the face of Horn's conciliatory approach, Vest insisted upon moral reparation from Felix Klein before any discussion could take place.

Letter 7 (Hungarian), 2 September, 1963, Budapest, Dr. Ferencz Horn to Dr. Mihály Pál Simon.

Horn refuted Vest's claims from the prior letter regarding the management of *Dr. Megyeri AG*, noting these were demonstrably false with contrary affidavits, business records, and official registers. Horn specifically contradicted Vest's assertion that the company had been liquidated, affirming this was neither documented nor known to board or authorities.¹³⁵ Horn asserted that Vest had no true claims on the company, was merely a bondholder, and that his liquidation sale was done independently.

Horn further rejected Vest's recent claims to ownership of the three paintings. He stated the works had been entrusted to Vest as "Jewish property" and demanded proof of legal acquisition, which Vest lacked. Horn explained his intervention was by the Klein family's request—to clarify the whereabouts of the paintings and the terms under which Vest might return them. Any return would require approval by the Hungarian National Bank.

Letter 8, 8 October, 1963, Budapest, Dr. Ferencz Horn to Dr. Mihály Pál Simon.

This final letter, known only through *Source 2*, documents that by October 1963 the painting had not been returned to the Klein family. Horn inquired explicitly whether the work was available for restitution and what price would be required for its release. He also noted his previous role as a board member of *Dr. Megyeri AG* in Kenyérmező.¹³⁶

LEGAL ASSESSMENT:

The documented restitution claims submitted by Felix Klein in the years 1947, 1956, and 1963 provide unequivocal evidence that the painting was neither voluntarily relinquished nor gifted. Rather, Fedor Vest had an explicit obligation to hold the work in trust. His refusal to return the painting despite repeated requests constitutes a culpable act of unlawful appropriation and represents a breach of the custodial relationship that existed between the parties.

The broader historical and political conditions in Hungary may have formed an external framework contributing to the failure to return the work. Following the communist takeover in 1949, property claims originating from the West—particularly those by Jewish émigrés—were systematically ignored or dismissed. While the right to private property continued to exist in a formal sense, its practical enforcement was severely constrained by state control, ideological restrictions, and the absence of an independent judiciary. In addition, Vest appears to have taken personal offense at the legal actions initiated against him by Felix and Otto Klein (see above), which evidently led him to break off all further communication.

Vest's conduct over the course of the restitution process appears particularly problematic. The surviving correspondence demonstrates that, over time, he advanced an evolving series of arguments in order to delay—or altogether avoid—the return of the Klimt painting. This strategic shifting of justifications indicates a clear underlying intent: Vest sought to defer, undermine, or ultimately derail the restitution process through inconsistent and self-serving reasoning. Such behavior must be regarded not only as morally questionable but also as a breach of good faith and fiduciary duty under legal standards. His role in this restitution case must therefore be considered especially sensitive and subject to critical scrutiny.

ON THE PERSON OF FEDOR VEST AND THE SUBSEQUENT OWNERSHIP OF THE PAINTING:

Dr. jur. Baron Fedor Miklós György Vest de Beoscin (Timișoara, 24 December, 1892 – Budapest, 27 June, 1969)¹³⁷ served as Counsellor at the Hungarian legation in Bucharest and occupied senior positions within the *Magyar Királyi Külügyminisztérium* ("Hungarian Ministry of Foreign Affairs"). A prominent figure in the diplomatic and aristocratic milieu of both Budapest and Bucharest, Vest also spent many years in Vienna, where his extravagant lifestyle and participation in elite salons were well known.

In the summer of 1919, Vest published the anti-communist pamphlet *Hogyan dolgoznak a bolsevisták?* ("How Do the Bolsheviks Work?"), an early testament to an ideological orientation characterized by pronounced national-conservatism and anti-Marxism.¹³⁸

A literary portrait of Fedor Vest can be found in a narrative text by the Hungarian writer and filmmaker András B. Vágvölgyi (b. 1959), which compellingly captures the ambivalence of Vest's character: As a dazzling dandy, brilliant master of languages, and "lion of society", he was—for a time—considered a bearer of hope for Hungarian–Romanian reconciliation. At the same time, he is depicted as a gambling-addicted impostor, restless and psychologically unstable. According to the text, Vest pawned imaginary real estate in Timișoara, suffered an economic downfall due to his gambling addiction, and was eventually placed under guardianship in Vienna. In his early activities in the environment of the Szeged counter-government, he was regarded as an outstanding expert in optant law matters—namely, the legal issues related to the selection of citizenship following the collapse of the monarchy. His anti-communist pamphlets were marked by reactionary language, in which he, for instance, referred to "degenerate art" and "cultural-political counter-selection". His subsequent isolation and economic decline stand in stark contrast to his earlier reputation as a brilliant diplomat, who was even praised by Prime Minister Gyula Maniu. In conclusion, Vágvölgyi describes him as a tragically grotesque figure caught between the role of diplomatic beacon of hope and personal downfall.¹³⁹

By the early 1930s, Vest's reputation had shifted to one of unreliability and moral dubiousness. Involvement in questionable financial schemes and defaults resulted in his dismissal from government service in 1932. That same year, he fled to Vienna and at times resided with his sister and brother-in-law¹⁴⁰—an arrangement that underscores his instability.¹⁴¹ At the behest of the Budapest police, he was later detained by Vienna authorities, though not extradited, as he claimed legal incapacity and avoided prosecution. On the advice of Julius Wagner-Jauregg,¹⁴² the renowned Austrian psychiatrist and Nobel laureate, he was repatriated to Budapest in June 1932 and committed to the *Angyalföld Psychiatric Hospital*,¹⁴³ from which he was released the following year. After the Second World War, Vest served for an indeterminate period as man-

aging director of *Dr. Megyeri AG*—a position that explains his connection to Felix and Otto Klein. In this context, apparent irregularities prompted Felix and Otto Klein to initiate legal proceedings against him, and as previously noted, he harbored enduring resentment toward them.

Vest first married Baroness Margit Mária Etelka Adél Olga Vest von Temesvár [Timișoara] (née Vojnits de Bajsa, 1890–1974), and in 1939, his second marriage was to Éva Vest (née Farkas¹⁴⁴, 1914–1988). Upon Fedor Vest’s death in 1969, ownership of the painting passed to *Custodian 1*.¹⁴⁵ After *Custodian 1*’s death in 1988, the painting was transferred to *Custodian 2*,¹⁴⁶ who, in 2005, passed it to *Custodian 3*.¹⁴⁷

REDISCOVERY AND OWNERSHIP STATUS SINCE 2022

According to Zsófia Végvári, the painting in question was rediscovered by Mr. G.¹⁴⁸, a Hungarian art historian, in the possession of *Custodian 3* in Budapest. The work was brought to scholarly attention in connection with an article by Thomas Trenkler, published in *Kurier* in 2015, under the title *Belvedere: Suche nach Klimts Häuptling der Aschanti* (“Belvedere: Searching for Klimt’s Chief of the Ashanti”),¹⁴⁹ where it was identified as a potentially significant painting by Gustav Klimt. To verify this presumption, Mr. G. suggested that the then-owner commission a technical examination of the painting, which was subsequently assigned to Zsófia Végvári. This investigation was carried out in two separate and chronologically structured phases, primarily in the early months of 2022 at her laboratory in Budapest. The final scientific examination report is dated 7 March, 2022.¹⁵⁰

As part of the authentication process, the owner also sought an initial expert opinion. Digital photographs of the painting were submitted to Ernst René Wastl and his wife, Eleni Korani, proprietors of *Ernst Galéria* in Budapest, a gallery with expertise in 19th- and 20th-century Hungarian art.¹⁵¹ Korani indicated that, in her view, the artwork could indeed be an authentic Klimt painting, though she did not pursue the matter further.¹⁵² At the same time, the painting was—according to communications to the author—brought to the attention of Bellák Gábor, art historian at the *Szépművészeti Múzeum* in Budapest and a court-certified expert on paintings. While one informant claimed that Bellák had contact with *Custodian 3*, and that he allegedly received two emails from *Custodian 3* in the matter, he informed the author in writing (29 May, 2025) that he was aware of the painting and its “very interesting history” only through media coverage. Additionally, the painting was submitted for review to the well-known Hungarian art historian Péter Molnos. In several public Facebook comments, Molnos commented on the work, particularly with respect to its export.¹⁵³ In direct communication with the author, however, Molnos clarified that he had never seen the painting in person.¹⁵⁴

In early July 2023, the painting was acquired by *Custodian 4*.¹⁵⁵ On 21 July, 2023, *Custodian 4* received an official export clear-

ance from the *Építési és Közlekedési Minisztérium – Műtárgyfelügyeleti Hatósági Főosztály* (“Ministry of Construction and Transport – Department for the Supervision of Cultural Objects”). The official confirmation stated that the export of the specifically identified objects, based on the data and photographs provided by the applicant, was not subject to any authorization requirement under Hungarian law. It was affirmed that, from the perspective of cultural heritage protection, the export was lawful and did not require a permit. This assessment was based on § 57 (1) of Act No. LXIV/2001 on the Protection of Cultural Heritage (Kötv.), which stipulates that the objects in question do not fall under the category of cultural goods requiring export authorization.¹⁵⁶

The export from Hungary and subsequent import into Austria by *Custodian 4* took place at the end of July 2023.¹⁵⁷ Shortly thereafter, I was granted the opportunity to undertake a close study of the then still unrestored painting in Vienna.¹⁵⁸ In December 2023, the painting underwent a further scientific examination; the author is in possession of the examination report (Report 113/2024) prepared by Katja Sterflinger from the *Institut für Naturwissenschaften und Technologie in der Kunst – Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien* (“Institute of Science and Technology in the Arts at the Academy of Fine Arts Vienna”).¹⁵⁹ The Klimt painting was then restored by conservator Alexander Storm, with restoration completed by February 2024. Since its return to Austria, the painting has been held in custodianship by the internationally operating art dealership *Wienerroither & Kohlbacher*, with locations in Vienna and New York.

In 2024, the Klimt painting was scheduled for its first public presentation since the *Klimt-Gedächtnisausstellung* (“Klimt Memorial Exhibition”) at the Vienna *Secession* in 1928. The work had already been physically transported to Maastricht for a planned showing at *TEFAF Maastricht* (7–14 March, 2024) but the presentation had to be cancelled when a settlement agreement between *Custodian 4* and the legal successors of Ernestine and Felix Klein could not be finalized in time. In contrast, the painting was successfully shown to the public at *TEFAF Maastricht 2025*, from 13 to 20 March, 2025 at booth 609 of *Wienerroither & Kohlbacher* at the MECC in Maastricht. The work was subsequently exhibited at *TEFAF New York*, at booth 308 in the *Park Avenue Armory*, from 8 to 13 May, 2025.

Between April and June 2025, a public debate unfolded regarding the circumstances of the export of the Klimt painting from Hungary to Austria. The discourse was catalyzed by a fact-based comment by Hungarian art historian Péter Molnos, posted on *Facebook* (see above), in which he, with scholarly circumspection, questioned how the work had legally left Hungary. He proposed for discussion whether, in the event of an officially approved export, a grave administrative oversight might have occurred—or, if no such approval had been granted, whether other equally serious circumstances merited investigation. Molnos’ wording was not personal accusation,

but rather a call for institutional clarification. His questions were subsequently echoed by several Hungarian and international media outlets, engendering an intense public discussion regarding possible breaches of export regulations or administrative failings.¹⁶⁰

Subsequently, the journalist Péter Hamvai, recognized for his thorough and impartial reporting, published several investigative pieces in the Hungarian weekly news magazine *Heti Világgazdaság* (*hvg*), in which he meticulously reconstructed the chronology of events using the available sources. In an article dated 13 June, 2025¹⁶¹, the Hungarian Minister of the *Építési és Közlekedési Minisztérium* (“Ministry of Construction and Transport”), János Lázár,¹⁶² stated it was not the role of the Hungarian state to contest ownership claims with Holocaust survivors or their descendants. Rather, in cases where a public institution such as the Hungarian *Szépművészeti Múzeum* might acquire the work, it should occur through fair and equitable agreement with the heirs (“a magyar állam úgy juthat hozzá, hogy az örökösökkel tisztességesen megegyezik”). By making this statement, he indirectly reaffirmed Hungary’s continued adherence to the *Washington Principles*, an international agreement adopted in December 1998, which provides essential recommendations for the identification, publication, and restitution of cultural property confiscated during the National Socialist era.¹⁶³ On 26 June, 2025, László Baán, Director of the *Szépművészeti Múzeum* in Budapest, publicly commented on the case and proposed the establishment of a national fund dedicated to the acquisition of artworks. In an interview led by Péter Hamvai,¹⁶⁴ the following statement was reported: “When asked whether he considers the purchase of the Klimt painting—currently in a private collection abroad—important, László Baán responded that it would be ideal and reassuring in the long term ‘if the Hungarian state were to quickly establish a national art acquisition fund with an annual budget equivalent to the cost of the Klimt painting—around 15 million euros.’ This would allow Hungary to release works of art domestically, support legal exports, and acquire outstanding works abroad.” This statement reflects Baán’s broader vision of strengthening Hungary’s cultural patrimony through sustained public investment, positioning the Klimt case within a larger discourse on national collecting policy and international art market dynamics.

The provenance of Gustav Klimt’s *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* unfolds as a complex and multilayered history shaped by artistic ambition, colonial exhibition culture, elite patronage, war-time expropriation, and postwar displacement. From its creation during the height of Vienna’s fin-de-siècle cosmopolitanism to its forced loss under National Socialist persecution, clandestine concealment in Hungary, and eventual re-emergence into the public sphere nearly a century later, the painting’s trajectory reflects the entangled histories of European modernism, colonial exhibition and trade practice, and Holocaust-era dispossession. Its reappearance invites renewed attention to unfinished histories—and to the

obligations that accompany the stewardship of cultural objects marked by displacement and dispossession.

APPENDIX A

VICTOR BAMBERGER’S ETHNOGRAPHIC EXHIBITION MODEL – FROM EXOTICISM TO IMMERSIVE SPECTACLE

Victor Bamberger recognized early the lucrative potential of so-called ethnographic exhibitions—spectacles now widely condemned for their racialising and dehumanising logic, which commodified the presence of African and other non-European individuals for predominantly white audiences in late 19th-century Europe. Modelled in part on the itinerant *Völkerschauen* developed by Hamburg-based animal trader Carl Hagenbeck in the 1870s, Bamberger adopted and transformed the format. He developed it into a scalable business model aimed at profit maximization. What set his approach apart was a shift from separation to interaction: from 1896 onward, he dismantled the physical barriers between performers and spectators, further intensifying the colonial gaze through enforced intimacy and proximity. This practice may be considered an early precursor to the format known today as the *Living Museum*, as found, for example, in Namibia¹⁶⁵ or South Africa, co-opting human presence for the spectacle of cultural difference.

Beginnings: The “African Village” at the 1896 Budapest Millennium Exhibition

Bamberger first documented involvement occurred in the context of the 1896 *Magyarország ezeréves fennállásának ünnepe* (“Budapest Millennium Exhibition”), where a so-called “African Village” was staged at the *Állatkert*.¹⁶⁶ Between 2 May and 31 October, it featured a group of about 250 West Africans led by the elders Bercsi and Kuako.¹⁶⁷ The operation was organized by Ferdinand Gravier, a French impresario active in Europe and the U.S. (see above). Later in 1897, he presented a group of Ashanti at the *Teatro Pizarro* in Valencia, Spain, having previously toured southern Europe. In the aftermath of this spectacle, Bamberger recruited approximately 70 members from the group for his own enterprise—an “Ashanti Village” constructed at the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* in Vienna’s *Prater*, as part of the *Kaiser-Jubiläums-Gewerbe-Ausstellung* (“Imperial Jubilee Exhibition”) (10 June–19 October, 1896). Featuring thatched huts, live crafts, and scripted performances of cultural practice, the exhibition was designed to project an illusion of colonial “authenticity”. It drew more than 250,000 visitors.

The 1897 “Ashanti Village”: Breakthrough in Vienna

Encouraged by his commercial success, Bamberger travelled personally to Accra, the capital of present-day Ghana, in the winter of 1896/97 where he recruited 120 individuals from the Osu district, including *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuo-*

na and his cousin Prince (Nortey) Emanuel W. R. Ababio. That summer, the “Ashanti Village” opened in Vienna to considerable public interest. It was during this time that Gustav Klimt and Franz Matsch produced their respective portraits of Prince Dowuona.

Bamberger eliminated the fences between the performers and the audience—a decisive departure from “standard exhibition practices.” This was not a gesture of inclusion, but a deliberate strategy to intensify affective and transactional contact, turning the site into a quasi-ethnographic marketplace. The audience could now move freely through the constructed village, interact with its inhabitants, and purchase hand-made goods. The “immersive presentation” should become a hallmark of Bamberger’s concept.

Expansion and Diversification: Prague, Graz, Berlin, and Hamburg (among others) (1897–1898)

At the peak of its popularity, Bamberger subdivided the group: a smaller ensemble—reportedly “15 men, 5 women, 8 girls, and 12 children”—led by Prince Ababio, travelled to Prague¹⁶⁸ (7 August to 5 September) and later to Graz¹⁶⁹ (7 September to 4 October), marking an early strategy of geographical diversification and exploitation of itinerant visibility.

Contrary to the widespread assumption that the group returned to Accra in full in 1897, newspaper reports indicate that in fact a part of them remained in Europe. In the feuilleton of the *Hamburger Freie Presse* (4 November, 1897), Moriz Findling reported on accompanying a “detachment” of Osu from Vienna to the steamship *Jeanette Woermann*,¹⁷⁰ which departed for West Africa on 31 October, 1897.¹⁷¹

As we know from numerous interviews undertaken by the author in Ghana, the Osu did not return home empty-handed. Many brought back items—both gifted and purchased—acquired during their time in Europe. These included European consumer goods, souvenirs, and items of personal significance. While the nature of their presence in Europe was fundamentally shaped by colonial voyeurism and economic exploitation, it is important to acknowledge that the participants also exercised limited forms of agency and negotiated spaces of relative autonomy within the tightly controlled structures of these exhibitions. Notably, “everyone, from the chief to the youngest baby, received a fixed wage: the two chiefs 10 pounds sterling each; the women 3 pounds; the young girls 1 pound 10 shillings; the men between 1.5 and 3 pounds; and each child 10 shillings per month, along with full board. Including the many monetary gifts from zoo visitors, their income significantly exceeded what Ashanti typically earned at home.”¹⁷² Moriz Findling, in an exaggerating manner, remarked in his commentary of 4 November, 1897: “They are returning to Accra [sic!] as wealthy people, for Dr. [Richard] Goldmann, the director of the zoo, paid out their handsome earnings in hard English gold. Even eight-year-old Akua, a charming light-brown girl, earned 2 pounds and 6 shillings.”¹⁷³ This rheto-

ric—typical of the time—must be read critically: the attribution of ‘wealth’ functioned to obscure the exploitative premises of the system while legitimising the conditions under which people had been put on display.

The Ashanti group that remained in Europe continued their work, now integrated with a Javanese ensemble. They travelled to Sweden to perform at Stockholm’s *Industrial Hall* (“Industrial Palace”) from 3 November, 1897. According to *Norrtelje Tidning* (4 November, 1897), around 100 individuals from the Gold Coast constructed huts in the rotunda.¹⁷⁴ The scale of the show suggests that additional individuals were recruited specifically for this venue—evidence of the impresarios’ logistical and organizational skills. The program largely followed the format previously shown in Vienna. Leadership reportedly rested with a “chief”, who performed with his wife and children, although his precise identity remains unconfirmed.¹⁷⁵

With a partially reassembled troupe, consisting of members who had stayed in Europe over the winter, as well as others who returned to Europe shortly after arriving back in Accra—joined by newly recruited individuals—Bamberger opened a new “Ashanti Village” at Berlin’s *Feen-Palast* on 2 March, 1898. It brought together around 90 participants from West Africa and was supplemented by a so-called “Javanese village”. A baptism held in Berlin was widely reported in the press and documented the presence of the group.¹⁷⁶

In August 1898, the troupe relocated to the *Zoologischer Garten* (“Zoological Garden”) in Hamburg. The exhibition, running from 31 August to 28 September, marked a new phase in the format’s evolution. Barriers between performers and spectators were again removed, and immersive interaction became central. The *Hamburger Fremdenblatt* praised this open structure as an improvement on earlier displays. In retrospect, this moment can be seen as anticipating the logic of the so-called *Living Museum*: daily life, ceremonial practices, and artisanal production (textiles, beadwork, goldsmithing, carving) were performed in real time—and offered for sale.¹⁷⁷ Here, the performers were not only objects of the colonial gaze but were also positioned as producers within a transactional setting that merged spectacle with market logic. Visitors assumed a dual role: that of observer and consumer. Press reports referred to the familiar “Vice-Chief Abebioh” and a “Chief named Nothei”, very likely the *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* portrayed by Klimt in the previous year.¹⁷⁸ According to the *Hamburger Echo* (21 October, 1898), Hamburg was likely the final stop: “The Ashanti troupe, which performed at the local zoological garden, is to depart today aboard the steamer *Anna Woermann* to return home.”¹⁷⁹ The actual departure occurred one day later, on 22 October.¹⁸⁰

Return to Prague and New Strategies (1899–1901)

The *Prager Tagblatt* reported that Bamberger returned to Accra again in the winter of 1898/99 to recruit a new group of

80 individuals.¹⁸¹ In March 1899, many members of the previous year's group returned to Europe.¹⁸² On April 29, 1899, the *Hamburgische Correspondent* reported that the mail steamer *Eduard Bohlen*,¹⁸³ operated by the *Woermann Line* which had just arrived in Hamburg from Loango (present-day Republic of the Congo), was carrying a larger group of individuals from the Ashanti people¹⁸⁴ who were to continue their journey to Vienna.¹⁸⁵ While their complete itinerary remains partially undocumented, several confirmed performances allow for a partial reconstruction of their tour. Following their arrival, the troupe is first documented in Leipzig, where they appeared at the *Zoologischer Garten* ("Zoological Garden") no earlier than May 11, 1899, and likely left the city shortly after June 3, 1899.¹⁸⁶ They subsequently performed in Breslau (present-day Wrocław), where daily shows were staged at the *Zoologischer Garten* ("Zoological Garden") between June 13 and July 19, 1899.¹⁸⁷ From there, they continued to Dresden, with confirmed performances at the *Zoologischer Garten* ("Zoological Garden") in the latter half of July.¹⁸⁸ Further stations included Königsberg (present-day Kaliningrad)¹⁸⁹ and Hamburg. In August, the troupe travelled to Prague, where they appeared on the "Hetzinsel" from August 15 to 30, 1899.¹⁹⁰ From 31 August, 1899, the Ashanti group performed again in Vienna,¹⁹¹ led by the "stately chief Nothei", presumably *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*.¹⁹² According to a schedule of attractions issued by the *Wiener Thiergarten* ("Vienna Zoological Garden") in September 1899, approximately 80 Ashanti individuals were "re-engaged" for the exhibition in the "Ashanti Village", purportedly "in response to popular demand."¹⁹³ The level of interaction had markedly increased since 1896, with Viennese visitors reportedly inviting the performers to dinner.¹⁹⁴ The group left Vienna on 2 October, 1899.

At the same time, Bamberger expanded his business model. He arranged for a so-called "Indian Village" to appear in *Hagenbeck's Menagerie* in Hamburg, a project coordinated in collaboration with Vienna's *Thiergarten*.¹⁹⁵

In 1901, Bamberger founded the company *The Ethnographical Show Co.* and, in collaboration with the New York-based impresario William Caspar, staged the monumental exhibition *Wild-Südafrika* ("Wild South Africa") in the *Riesen-Arena* at the *Urania Park* in Vienna.¹⁹⁶ As one contemporary report noted, "Mr. William Caspar, with his vivid presentation *Wild South Africa*, in which local Zulu, Matabele, Bafuto, etc., appear within ethnographically accurate settings, has created an extraordinary attraction for Vienna."¹⁹⁷ Following a preliminary performance in May 1901,¹⁹⁸ the show ran four consecutive weeks until 14 July, 1901, after which the troupe travelled to Budapest for another three-week engagement. Additional performances were held in Vienna¹⁹⁹ before the "exhibition" was ultimately transferred to Frankfurt.²⁰⁰ These new cycles of departure and return highlight how the exhibitions were not isolated events but formed part of a transcontinental system of circulation shaped by colonial desire and capital flow.

The Sultan Ali Troupe (1904): Flexibility as Principle

After the abrupt cancellation of a planned Ashanti show in Bradford (UK), Victor Bamberger travelled with the British adventurer Captain Charles Holland Hastings (b. 1860) to Aden (in present-day Yemen).²⁰¹ There, he assembled a new troupe composed of individuals from British Somaliland and French-controlled Djibouti. This group was led by Sultan Ali al-Urfur, a polyglot impresario with personal experience in the colonial exhibition business. Comprising a total of 57 individuals, it served as a substitute for the cancelled Ashanti ensemble—an illustration of Bamberger's capacity to swiftly reconfigure his programming based on available resources and market conditions.

The troupe arrived in France on 23 February, 1904 and subsequently performed for two months, first in Nice and then in Marseille. According to Bamberger's own account, and with the alleged support of his wife²⁰² the group won the *Bataille de Fleurs* competition during the Nice carnival on 25 February—a claim that, lacking corroboration in the French Press, is likely to have been promotional fiction.²⁰³ From 3 April to 1 May, 1904, the troupe performed in the gardens of the *Château-des-Fleurs* at the *Rond-Point de Prado* in Marseille, before finally arriving in Bradford on 3 May.

Conceptual Innovation: The Dissolution of Distance

As previously noted, Bamberger's most notable innovation lay in dismantling the physical and symbolic barriers between "visitors" and "performers". While early Hagenbeck-style exhibitions employed fences and palisades, by the 1890s these were increasingly replaced by simple wooden enclosures.

As early as 1896, at the "Ashanti Village" in Vienna's *Prater*, a low fence reminiscent of horse paddocks replaced traditional barriers. Visitor contact with the troupe was still limited. By 1897, however, Bamberger had removed all fencing, allowing visitors to move freely through the reconstructed village. At least nine gouaches by Wilhelm Gause (1853–1916), created in June 1897 for the *Illustrierte [sic!] Woche* to accompany an article on the "Ashanti Village"²⁰⁴—and of which at least one preserved in the *Wien Museum*²⁰⁵ (fig. 13)—vividly capture this shift in staging, offering not only a dynamic visual record of the exhibition's theatrical *mise-en-scène* but also insight into contemporary strategies of ethnographic spectacle and visual narration in the *fin-de-siècle* press. Strikingly, Gause's works reveal how visitors themselves—much like in today's concept of a *Living Museum*—became an integral part of the performative environment, blurring the boundaries between observer and observed. This participatory mode of representation marked a significant departure from earlier forms of colonial display, which Sadiah Qureshi has described as "staged otherness"—a practice that "rendered the non-European subject as both radically different and visually accessible, but always within a rigid framework of imperial hierarchies."²⁰⁶ In contrast, the 1897 "Ashanti Village" in Vienna

Fig. 13: Wilhelm Gause, *Scene of the “Ashanti Village” with Vendor Booths*, June 1897
Wien Museum

staged a more immersive, seemingly interactive encounter, which Gause’s illustrations capture with remarkable acuity.

This transformation was not guided by emancipatory intent, but by commercial logic. The more seamlessly an “authentic encounter” could be simulated, the greater the audience engagement—and, consequently, the financial return. Photographs and artistic renderings from the Vienna “Ashanti Village” of 1896 and 1897 (see above) attest to this progressive shift in scenographic design. In 1898, the *Hamburger Fremdenblatt* praised the updated layout: “The public can move freely in the Negro village, and better than ever can they gain an impression of the customs and lifestyles of the African tribe.”²⁰⁷

Bamberger thus implemented an exhibition model that may be regarded as a direct precursor to today’s *Living Museums*: minimal barriers, immersive layouts, and curated interactivity. Yet these elements must be understood within the asymmetrical frameworks of colonial display. While the performances claimed to offer “cultural proximity”, they did so through a lens shaped by European fantasies of the racial and geographic “Otherness”. The illusion of access—of intimacy without reciprocity—was a defining element of the genre.

Sources and Research Gaps

Victor Bamberger remains an understudied figure in the history of commercial ethnographic exhibition. He epitomizes a category of European impresarios who combined the entertainment strategies of popular spectacle with the representational logics of colonial ideology. Despite the growing availability of digitized historical newspapers, documentation of Bamberger’s networks, logistical strategies, and the experiences of the performers he recruited remains fragmentary.

What is still largely missing is a systematic study that centres the voices, experiences, and afterlives of those who travelled and performed under his direction. Such research is urgently needed to shift the analytical focus from the spectacle itself to the historical subjects who, even within restrictive and often exploitative conditions, acted and negotiated their conditions.

APPENDIX B

THE DR. MEGYERI LANDWIRTSCHAFTLICHE INDUSTRIE AG IN KENYÉRMEZŐ

The Hungarian joint-stock company *Dr. Megyeri Mezőgazdasági R.T.* (“Dr. Megyeri Landwirtschaftliche Industrie AG”), headquartered in Kenyérmező near Esztergom, formed a key economic milieu through which much of the Hungarian provenance chain of the Klimt painting once owned by Ernestine and Felix Klein can be substantially reconstructed. Although the corporation was formally established on 1 September, 1920,²⁰⁸ the Klein family’s connections with its business structure date back considerably earlier. Even before the company’s legal founding, Felix and Otto Klein were involved in the business activities of Dr. Izidor Megyeri (see below) and were among the early investors in his agro-industrial enterprise.

Dr. Izidor (Krausz) Megyeri (1854–1920),²⁰⁹ a prominent Hungarian entrepreneur of Jewish origin, acquired the Kenyérmező estate near Esztergom in November 1886 from the railway director Maximilian Ritter Fuchs von Bánrét (1831–1887).²¹⁰ By 1887, more than 600 laborers were employed on the estate and in the associated distillery.²¹¹ In 1890, he established the *Krausz Spiritus & Presshefe Factory* in Kenyérmező. His approach combined agricultural industrialisation with

strong social engagement—evident, for instance, in his 1902 founding of a school in Kenyérmezőmajor for the children of agricultural workers. In Budapest, Megyeri owned several properties and resided in a grand villa at Andrásy út 109. His monumental tomb, created by the sculptor János Horvay (1874–1944), at the *Kerepesi Cemetery* in Budapest is located directly behind the mausoleum of Ferenc Deák.

The extent and structure of the estate are vividly illustrated in a cadastral map of the city of Esztergom from 1902, preserved in the Komárom–Esztergom County Archives.²¹² The map depicts the schematic layout of 78 contiguous landholdings south of Esztergom, including the Kenyérmező and Sátorkő–Pusztas, which constituted the core of the Megyeri landholdings.

Following Megyeri's death, his business operations were consolidated into *Dr. Megyeri AG*, founded in 1920. Felix and Otto Klein became dominant shareholders and assumed key managerial roles. Their names appear in the Budapest commercial register well before the company's official founding, and by 1927 they were formally listed on the board.²¹³ Another key figure was Dr. Ferencz Horn (see above)—he would later serve as legal counsel to Felix Klein in the matter of restitution—and held the position of legal advisor and board member within the company.

Arthur János Duff, a further central actor, appears in a letter dated 22 June, 1938 from Vienna-based attorney Dr. Friedrich Wedl to the *Staatskommissariat für die Privatwirtschaft* (“State Commissioner for Private Industry”) concerning the Aryanisation of *Klein & Brandl AG*.²¹⁴ The letter reports that Duff, identified as a British national, had formally acquired Felix Klein's shares in *Dr. Megyeri AG* as early as 1935, with the transfer finalised in 1936. However, the circumstances strongly suggest that this transaction was backdated, primarily serving to shield Felix Klein's assets from seizure under anti-Semitic policies.²¹⁵ Duff reappears—according to the minutes of the general meeting on 14 October, 1940—alongside Otto Klein and others as a board member in the *Magyar Királyi Cégjegyzék* (“Hungarian commercial register”).²¹⁶ At that time, Dr. jur. Fedor Vest, a figure central to the ownership history of the Klimt painting, held executive leadership of the firm – he plays a crucial role in the ownership history of the Klimt painting (see above).

The continuity among the investors, administrative personnel, and legal representatives of the company and the principal actors in the Klimt provenance narrative is indeed noteworthy. Nearly all relevant individuals—Felix and Otto Klein, Dr. Ferencz Horn, Arthur János Duff, Irene Endrédi, Dr. Mihály Pál Simon, and *Baron Dr. jur. Fedor Vest*—were, at various times, directly associated with the *Dr. Megyeri AG*. This network may be regarded as the institutional and economic backbone of the Klein family's attempt at safeguarding their art collection and other assets.

Even after Megyeri's death in 1920, the company remained operational. Its headquarters were located in Budapest, initially at Veres Pálné utca 17, later at Bálvány utca 22.²¹⁷ As late as 1939, plans were underway to subdivide large tracts of company land in Kenyérmező for workers' housing.²¹⁸ In 1941, a request was filed for the construction of a mineral grinding facility in Esztergom.²¹⁹ This continuity attests to the company's ongoing economic significance even amid political upheaval. No documents have yet been located concerning the company's final liquidation, though Fedor Vest would almost certainly have played a role, given his position as managing director.

Reconstructing the history of *Dr. Megyeri AG* offers crucial insight into the socio-economic environment within which the Klein collection—and the Klimt painting in particular—was accumulated, preserved, and contested. The company operated not only as a business platform but as a protective structure within an increasingly hostile political landscape. Further archival research is necessary to illuminate the company's legal transformations and to critically assess its function in the context of this provenance research.

REFERENCES

- 1 The *Thiergarten am Schüttel* in the Vienna *Prater* opened in 1863. It experienced only moderate success until the ethnological exhibitions with the *Ashanti*, and had to close periodically due to financial difficulties.
- 2 In 1893, the *Matabele* (then officially known as the *Matabele* under British rule; today normally referred to as the *Ndebele* or *amaNdebele*) from Matabeleland (present-day: Zimbabwe) were defeated by British colonial troops. The death of their king, Lobengula, in 1894 left the population in a state of collapse. The African traveler Dr. B. Meyer exploited the situation by asking the tribal leader Saidrovuni and 25 *Matabele* to tour Europe. After a stay in Düsseldorf, the group made a guest appearance in Vienna from January to May 1895. See, for example, “Wiener Thiergarten”, *Neue Freie Presse* (Vienna: 24 May, 1895), 2.
- 3 The principal owners were Anton Dreher the Younger (1849–1921) and Adolf Freiherr Bachofen von Echt (1864–1947), who later became the husband of Elisabeth Lederer. Elisabeth Lederer was portrayed by Gustav Klimt between 1914 and 1916. See: Alfred Weidinger, *Gustav Klimt – Catalogue Raisonné of the Paintings* (Munich/Berlin/London/New York: 2007), cat. no. 227.
- 4 For more on such exhibitions of foreign peoples (in the 19th century, the term *foreign peoples* referred to those described as *exotic* or *primitive*—categories shaped by colonial ideology and Eurocentric worldviews) in Vienna, see, for example: Werner Michael Schwarz, *Anthropologische Spektakel. Zur Schaustellung ‘exotischer’ Menschen, Vienna 1870–1910* (Vienna: 2001).
- 5 The French impresario Ferdinand Gravier, founder of several trading companies along the Guinean coast, arranged the *Ashanti* guest performance in collaboration with the administration of the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* in Vienna's *Prater*.
- 6 In several contemporary newspaper reports, his surname is also mistakenly spelled as “Bouvier”. See: “Die Aschanti”, in *Morgen-Presse*, no. 189 (Vienna: 11 July, 1896), 4; and “Aschanti in Wien”, in *Arbeiter-Zeitung*, no. 189 (Vienna: 11 July, 1896), 4.
- 7 See: Appendix A.
- 8 R. Lechner, *Ankunft einer Gruppe von ca. 70 Aschanti per Schiff am Donaukanal zu vorübergehendem Exoten-Aufenthalt im Wiener Thiergarten*, (Original caption by the photographer), (“Arrival of a group of approximately 70 Ashanti by ship at the Danube Canal for a temporary stay as ‘exotic guests’ in the Vienna Zoo”), ÖNB Vienna, Bildarchiv, <http://data.onb.ac.at/rec/baa10089836>.

- 9 "Die Aschanti", in *Morgen-Press*, no. 189 (Vienna: 11 July 1896), 4
- 10 "Den Besuchern des an Attraktionen so reichen Wiener Thiergartens wird sich Sonntag den 12. d. M. (Juli) ein eigenartiges Schauspiel bieten. Die Bevölkerung eines afrikanischen Dorfes von ungefähr 70 Ashanti-Negern wird dort ihr Tagewerk wie im Heimatdorf verrichten. Die Männer fertigen mit ihren primitiven Werkzeugen bunte Gewebe, kunstvolle Schmiedearbeiten und Goldschmuck an oder erholen sich bei nationalen Spielen und Kriegstänzen, während die Frauen vor den Augen des Publikums die Mahlzeiten zubereiten." *Der Humorist* (Vienna, 10 July, 1896), 4. ("Visitors to Vienna's Tiergarten, which offers so many attractions, will be treated to a remarkable spectacle on Sunday 12th [July]. The 'population' of an African village—about 70 Ashanti Negroes—will go about their daily routines as in their home village. The men will use their basic tools to create colourful textiles, ornate metalwork, and gold jewelry, or relax with national games and war dances, while the women prepare meals in front of the public.")
- 11 The event was advertised in daily newspapers: "Große ethnographische Schaustellung: Ashanti-Dorf. Eingeborene Männer, Frauen und Kinder, Industrie, Schule, nationale Spiele, Kriegstänze und Gefechte" ("Great ethnographic display: Ashanti village. Native men, women and children, industry, school, national games, war dances and battles.") *Kikeriki*, advertisement supplement to no. 62 (Vienna: 2 August, 1896). Detailed accounts of these performances come from contemporary newspaper reports as well as period photographs, drawings, and postcards. Particularly revealing is the short film *Ashanti Martial Knife Dance*, produced in 1897 during an Ashanti exhibition in Lyon (Perrache), which vividly illustrates how such performances were staged. See: "1897 Ashanti Martial Knife Dance", Exhibition France (Film date 17 April, 1897 – 2 May, 1897), video, 1:05, British Pathé, May 13, 2015. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XKy1BqyODcc>.
- 12 The Ethnographic exhibition was such a success that the organisers decided to invite another 25 "Ashanti" for the *Großes Kaiserfest* ("Great Imperial Festival") on 18 August, 1896, and to expand the village accordingly.
- 13 Peter Altenberg, *Ashantee* (Berlin: 1897). See: Marilyn Scott, "A Zoo Story: Peter Altenberg's Ashantee" (1897), in *Modern Austrian Literature* 30, no. 2 (Lincoln: 1997), 48–64, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24648666>.
- 14 Robert Franceschini, "Ashanti-Fieber", in *Neues Wiener Tagblatt* (Vienna: 7 October, 1896), 1-3.
- 15 The background of this group and details of their recruitment remain unknown. What is certain, however, is that its members stayed in Vienna until the end of the "Ashanti Village" exhibition at the *Prater*. For the Emperor's birthday, the press reported (August 18, 1896): "Die interessanteste Nummer des im Wiener Thiergarten stattfindenden Kaiserfestes dürfte der um 9 Uhr Abend auf der Reitbahn von der Aschanti-Truppe zur Darstellung gelangende Fetisch-Tanz sein." ("The most interesting event of the imperial celebration [Kaiserfest] in the Vienna Thiergarten will probably be the fetish dance performed at 9 p.m. by the Aschanti troupe in the riding arena." See: "Wiener Thiergarten", *Morgen-Press*, no. 226 (Vienna: 18 August, 1896), 5.
- 16 Aschanti-Dorf im Wiener Thiergarten" (Ashanti Village in the Viennese Zoological Garden), *Neues Wiener Tagblatt* (Tages-Ausgabe) (Vienna: 23 August, 1896), 13.
- 17 Peter Altenberg, *Ashantee* – (Im Wiener Thiergarten bei den Negern der Goldküste.) (Berlin: 1897).
- 18 P. Altenberg 1897, [71]. It is striking that Altenberg consistently applied diacritical marks to nearly all personal names in his book *Ashantee*. While the Ga language does occasionally use accents to indicate tone, Altenberg's spelling diverges significantly from the original. He likely followed his own phonetic interpretation rather than established orthographic norms.
- 19 P. Altenberg 1897, [63].
- 20 Once again, the political situation of an African tribe was exploited. The King of the Ashanti, Kwaku Dua III Asamu, known as Agyeman Prempeh I (1870–1931), was captured by the British army in January 1896. He was deported first to the coastal town of Elmina and later to the *Colony and Protectorate of Sierra Leone*. The British then declared the former Ashanti Kingdom a protectorate.
- 21 See, among others, the following publications: "Accra: Political Structure and Mantsemei, 1860s–1920s", in John Parker, *Making the Town. Ga State and Society in Early Colonial Accra* (Oxford 2000), and Marion Kilson, "African Urban Kinsmen. The Ga of Central Accra" (London: 1974).
- 22 Ashley Dawson, *Shifting Sands: The Politics of Belonging and the African Diaspora in the Postcolonial City of Accra*, PhD diss. (London: 2001), table 1, 26.
- 23 The *Neue Freie Presse* in Vienna reported on 7 July that a letter had arrived from the Gold Coast reporting the death of the "first tribal chief King Dowonnah of Osu", who was a "cousin of the chief Nothei Dowonnah" then staying in Vienna. *Neue Freie Presse* (Vienna: 7 July, 1897), 6.
- 24 His successor as *Osu Mantse* was Nii Nortey Ababio II, who ruled from 1900 to 1914.
- 25 With regard to the ethnic origin of the individuals exhibited in the so-called "Ashanti Villages" across Europe, it must be emphasized that further in-depth research is required in order to draw nuanced and substantiated conclusions. A preliminary review of contemporary press reports reveals numerous personal names that suggest origins in other West African ethnic groups—most notably among the Ga people, particularly individuals from Osu. In addition, iconographic analyses of historical photographs indicate that clothing and adornments do not consistently conform to the characteristic features of *Ashanti* cultural expression. Taken together, the available evidence already allows for a reasonably certain conclusion: the *Ashanti* presented at the Vienna *Thiergarten* were in fact predominantly members of the Ga community—specifically from Osu—and that the term *Ashanti*, as discussed elsewhere in this text, functioned primarily as a familiar and exoticizing label within the European context, employed to enhance public interest and marketability.
- 26 *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona* was the son of *Osu Mantse* Nii Noi Dowuona II (Fetreké) who reigned from 1851 to 1868.
- 27 BW, "Die Wiener bei den Aschantis", *Neue Freie Presse* (Vienna: 23 May, 1897), 6-7, 6. In contemporary newspapers, the spelling of his name varies—such as "Abebioh", "Abebio", or "Ababio". Sometimes his official surname "Nortey" is omitted in favor of his baptismal names "Emanuel W.R."
- 28 The *Osu Mantse* is still appointed on a rotating basis by the two royal families, the *House of Amantra* and the *House of Kinkawe*.
- 29 The *Gertrud Woermann* was a steamship of the German *Woermann Line*, a Hamburg-based shipping company that was one of the major players in African trade. The ship was built by *Vulcan AG* in Stettin and launched in 1885. It operated between Germany, West Africa, and South Africa until 1903, when it ran aground near Port Nolloth, South Africa. Individual passenger lists exist in archives, but those for 1897 have not yet been found.
- 30 Victor Bamberger had concluded an annual contract with the *Ashanti*, which enabled him to exhibit the troupe in other cities. The exhibition opened with the seasonal reopening of the *Thiergarten am Schüttel* in Vienna's *Prater* on Easter Sunday, April 18, 1896.
- 31 Bamberger used the term *Ashanti* less in an ethnographic sense than as a promotional label. Regardless of their actual origin, all West African groups were marketed under this designation. Ethnographic accuracy was entirely subordinated to economic interests—a typical feature of colonial exhibition practices. This promotional label proved to be highly monetizable: in the Vienna and later in the other European cities where Bamberger staged the "Ashanti Village," at least seven different postcards featuring motifs from the Vienna installation were published by a dedicated "Verlag der Wiener Thiergarten-Verwaltung."
- 32 The next guest performance was to take place in Stockholm (see: Appendix A).
- 33 Carl Hagenbeck organised the exhibition of a Nubian caravan for the Vienna *Rotunda* in 1878. On 20 June, 1878, the *Presse* newspaper reported: "Der Hamburger Thierhändler Hagenbeck hat vom Handelsministerium die Erlaubnis erhalten, dem Wiener Publicum in der Rotunde eine jener Thierkarawanen vorzuführen, die er aus dem Inneren Afrikas nach Europa bringt, um hier die zoologischen Gärten und Menagerien mit dem nötigen Nachwuchs zu versehen. Die Karawane besteht aber nicht nur aus afrikanischen Thieren, sondern auch aus Eingeborenen nubischen Stammes, welche den Transport und die Wartung der Thiere besorgen." (My translation: "The Hamburg animal dealer Hagenbeck has received permission from the Ministry of Trade to present one of his animal caravans, brought from the interior of Africa to Europe, to the Viennese public in the *Rotunda*, in order to provide the zoological gardens and menageries with the necessary stock. The caravan consists not only of African animals but also of Nubian natives who care for and transport the animals." "The African animal caravan in the rotunda". *Local-Anzeiger of the Presse*. Supplement to no. 167 (Vienna: 20 June, 1878), [9]-10.
- 34 The reason for Alfred Sappor's continued stay in Vienna appears to have been due less to his personal choice and more to the intervention of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*. Sappor was reportedly involved in a relationship with "Debe", Dowuona's wife, which may have played a role in his being left behind in Vienna. Research in Viennese archives has yielded no evidence of Sappor's naturalization, so it is assumed he departed Vienna at the next available opportunity—either by joining another troupe or returning directly to Accra via Hamburg.
- 35 The name of the Osu prince from Accra, *William Nii Nortey Dowuona*, appeared in varied spellings at the time, ranging from "William Rothe Dowoonah" (See: "Praterbilder", *Neue Freie Presse* [Vienna: 18 April, 1897], 8) to "Note Devinnah" ("Der Wiener Thiergarten", *Kikeriki*, no. 45 [Vienna: 6 June, 1897]).
- 36 One of the most significant private collections of photographs and documents related to so-called "human zoos" is the *Radauer Collection*. This online archive is based on the private collection assembled by Clemens Radauer over the past several years. It comprises postcards, photographs, publicity materials, program leaflets, and press articles documenting human zoos from the 1870s to the 1930s. The collection can be accessed online at: https://humanzoos.net/?page_id=4315
- 37 Kind remark by *Osu Mantse* Notse Nii Nortey Owuo IV during an interview held on 18 April, 2025 in Osu, Accra.
- 38 See: Thomas Trenkler, "Belvedere: Suche nach Klimts Häuptling der Aschanti"

- (“Search for Klimt’s Chief of the Ashanti”), *Kurier* (Vienna: 13 September, 2015), online: <https://kurier.at/kultur/belvedere-suche-nach-klimts-hauptling-der-ashanti/152.471.545>.
- 39 The Viennese art dealer and art historian Herbert Giese referenced this painting under the title *Nubier mit Umhangtuch* (“Nubian Wearing a Cloak”) in his dissertation *Franz v. Matsch - Leben und Werk* (Vienna: 1976). It was first depicted in a black-and-white photo in a 1972 *Dorotheum* auction catalogue in Vienna, where it was titled *Der junge Negerhäuptling* (“The Young Negro Chief”). This title was pivotal for targeted research in Ghana.
- 40 The portrait was auctioned at the *Dorotheum* in Vienna on 10/23 June, 1972 (lot 82, fig. plate 1).
- 41 One of the earliest pairs of portraits is the *Bildnis eines Mädchen mit Spitzenkragen* (“Portrait of a Girl with a Lace Collar”), created around 1870. See: Alfred Weidinger, “Ernst Klimt – Aspekte eines kurzen Künstlerlebens” (“Aspects of a Short Artistic Life”), in: *Gustav Klimt und die Künstler-Compagnie* (Vienna and Weitra: 2007), 90-121, ill. 94-95).
- 42 Richard Hoisel, “Zum Gedächtnis Gustav Klimts” (“In Memory of Gustav Klimt”), *Wiener Woche*, issue 5 (Vienna: 1919), 4-5, ill. on p. 4. Acknowledgements to Barbara Marx and Laura Erhold of the *Klimt-Foundation* Vienna for drawing attention to this publication.
- 43 Gustav Klimt did not leave a will. The probate file from the relevant district court—which might have contained information about the artistic estate he left behind—has unfortunately been lost. Klimt’s legal heirs consisted of his four surviving siblings (Georg, Klara, Hermine and Johanna) and his three illegitimate children. It is widely believed that his brother, Georg (an artist himself), took responsibility for managing the artistic estate and distributed the works among the siblings. Several drawings bear handwritten ownership marks attributed to Klimt’s siblings. Due to the missing documents and the passage of time, it is now impossible to precisely reconstruct which specific works by Gustav Klimt were inherited by each heir—including the portrait of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*.
- 44 Alice Strobl, *Gustav Klimt. The Drawings, Supplement 1878–1918* (Salzburg: 1989), 220.
- 45 With thanks to Alexander Storm, Pressbaum (AT), for this information.
- 46 See: Alfred Weidinger, “Sonja Knips”, in *Gustav Klimt – 150 Jahre*, Agnes Husslein-Arco and Alfred Weidinger (eds.) (Vienna: 2012), 74-77, 76.
- 47 Weidinger 2007, no. 116.
- 48 Weidinger 2007, no. 117.
- 49 Weidinger 2007, no. 118.
- 50 The three-part television series was commissioned by *Red Bull Media House* (Salzburg) and produced by *TV&More* (Vienna).
- 51 At the time, the *Osu Maytse* expressed the intention to share these objects. However, following his death and the succession of a new *Osu Maytse*, access was made contingent on a payment of EUR 30,000. According to personal correspondence from *The Dowuona Royal House* dated 8 April, 2025: “Given the historical weight, cultural relevance, and exclusive access to family-held materials; both oral and archival, we expect a full compensation of EUR 30,000 for our involvement in the documentary.”
- 52 The position of *Osu Maytse* is filled on a rotating basis from the two royal families.
- 53 In collaboration with *Osu Maytse* Notse Nii Nortey Owuo, I am currently developing an exhibition project and a publication focusing on the history of this portrait. The project centers not only on the biography of *Prince William Nii Nortey Dowuona*—as depicted in two paintings—and his role within the *Osu* community of Greater Accra, but also on the context of his journey to Europe in the context of the ethnographic exhibition staged in Vienna in 1897 and subsequent years in various European cities. Beyond this, the project addresses the *Osu* community’s place in this colonial spectacle, as well as contemporary perspectives from the descendants of those involved. The precise identification of the prince and his entourage, together with tracing their descendants in Ghana, enables a reframing of the 1897 “Völker-schau” beyond a purely Eurocentric view, encouraging a multi-perspective, critical reflection on this colonial chapter in European exhibition practice. The project thus aims to contribute to a decolonial culture of memory by revealing historical imbalances and interrogating established narratives.
- 54 Of particular note is the fact that the *Osu* also left objects behind in Vienna. During my research, I made significant discoveries at the *Weltmuseum* Vienna in February 2024. In 1896 and 1897, the former *k. k. Naturhistorisches Hofmuseum* (“Imperial and Royal Natural History Court Museum”) received a total of 27 objects, mediated by the Viennese lawyer Dr. Richard Goldmann, all originating from the “Ashanti Village” at the *Thiergarten am Schüttel*. These included arrowheads, bowls, sandals, and musical instruments. Special thanks are due to Christian Schicklgruber and Peter Kloser of the *Weltmuseum* Vienna, whose meticulous work in the historical inventory books made it possible to identify these objects.
- 55 Ashley Dawson, *Shifting Sands: The Politics of Belonging and the African Diaspora in the Postcolonial City of Accra*, PhD diss. (London: 2001), table 1, 26.
- 56 A. Dawson 2001, table 1, 26.
- 57 Herbert Giese, *Franz v. Matsch – Leben und Werk*, Dissertation (Wien: 1976).
- 58 With thanks to Ruud Priem, Department Head and Curator of Fine Art at the *Musée National d’Histoire et d’Art* (MNAHA), Luxembourg, for his valuable remarks, dated 31 March, 2025.
- 59 The suggestion of Nikolaus Dumba as a possible patron was first brought to my attention by Herbert Giese, Vienna (email to the author, 30 March, 2025).
- 60 Weidinger 2007, no. 94.
- 61 Weidinger 2007, no. 95.
- 62 Weidinger 2007, no. 119.
- 63 Weidinger 2007, no. 130.
- 64 The *Künstler-Compagnie* (“Artists’ Company”) was a formal artistic partnership founded in the early 1890s by Gustav Klimt, his younger brother Ernst Klimt and Franz Matsch. The three artists collaborated on numerous monumental decorative commissions for public and private buildings, including theaters and museums across the Austro-Hungarian Empire. Their style, grounded in academic historicism, later evolved—particularly in the case of Gustav Klimt—towards a more modern and symbolist aesthetic. The *Künstler-Compagnie* represents a formative phase in Klimt’s career, bridging the academic traditions of the Ringstraße era with the emergence of Viennese modernism. See: Agnes Husslein-Arco and Alfred Weidinger (eds.), *Gustav Klimt und die Künstler-Compagnie* (Wien and Weitra: 2007). And in particular regarding the dissolution of the *Künstler-Compagnie*, see: Alfred Weidinger, “Resignation und Aufbruch – Das Ende der Compagnie” (Resignation and Transition – The Final Chapter of the Compagnie), in: Agnes Husslein-Arco and Alfred Weidinger (eds.), *Gustav Klimt und die Künstler-Compagnie* (Wien and Weitra: 2007), 122-133.
- 65 Provenance: Nikolaus Dumba, Vienna (until 1900). – Private collection. – *Galerie Grünangergasse* (Kurt Kalb), Vienna (acquired at the *Dorotheum* auction on June 20, 1972). – *Shepherd Gallery* (Robert Kashey), New York (acquired in the early 1970s from Kurt Kalb). – Collection of Winthrop Kellogg Edey (1938–1999), New York (acquired from *Shepherd Gallery*). – Private ownership. – *Sotheby’s*, New York, 13 October, 2020, Lot 22 (unsold). – *Sotheby’s*, New York, 15–25 October, 2021 (online auction), Lot 511. – *Musée national d’archéologie, d’histoire et d’art* (MNAHA), Luxembourg (acquired at *Sotheby’s*, New York).
- 66 The author thanks for informations provided by Robert Kashey (*Shepherd Gallery*, New York), March 31, 2025 and from Olga Kronsteiner (*Der Standard*), April 7, 2025.
- 67 Special thanks to Olga Kronsteiner (*Der Standard*) for pointing out that the *Bundesdenkmalamt* (“Federal Monuments Office”) in Vienna registered no export application for this painting by Franz Matsch between 1948 and 1974.
- 68 Kind note from Robert Kashey (*Shepherd Gallery*, New York), dated March 31, 2025.
- 69 Sincere thanks to Ruud Priem, for notification after the acquisition and granting access to the portrait and documentation. The portrait, following restoration, is now on display in the museum’s permanent collection (inv. no 2021-265/001).
- 70 Dumba, Nikolaus: Testament. *Bezirksgericht Innere Stadt* (“Last Will and Testament, District Court of the Inner City”) Testament 38/1900, *Wiener Stadt- und Landesarchiv* (“Municipal and Provincial Archives of Vienna”), H.A.-Akten – Persönlichkeiten, D 8, Nikolaus Dumba.
- 71 Grateful acknowledgment to Maria Polsterer-Kattus, Vienna, 22 April, 2025.
- 72 Information courtesy of Katja Zirnsack, *Dorotheum*, Vienna, 2 May, 2025.
- 73 In this text, the historically and violently charged term *Neger* (“Negro”) is spelled out in full with utmost caution and critical intent. This choice is not made lightly; it arises from a scholarly commitment to engage directly with the language of colonial-era documents, exhibitions, and institutional discourses, in order to confront their racialising structures without euphemism or erasure. The term appears exclusively in clearly demarcated historical or archival contexts—such as in direct quotations from primary sources or references to period-specific titles and self-descriptions. Its presence in the text is neither normalised nor affirmed, and the use of its language is always accompanied by explicit contextualisation, with the aim of dismantling rather than reproducing the racialised epistemologies that have shaped both historical and scholarly narratives.
- 74 My colleague Markus Feller, from the *Research Center* at the *Belvedere* in Vienna, located a copy of the auction catalogue with illustrations after our intensive research into Gustav Klimt’s early work.
- 75 Ernestine Klein, née Kreisler. Historical Viennese registration documents in the *Wiener Stadt- und Landesarchiv* (“Municipal and Provincial Archives of Vienna”). Father: Josef Kreisler (December 1850–29 April, 1926). Mother: Anna Netty, née Neyer (18 October, 1856 – 9 September, 1935).
- 76 The art historian and conservator Robert Eigenberger was also active as an artist and was a member of the *Vienna Secession* between 1928 and 1939. Beginning in 1933, he directed the conservation courses at the *Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien* (“Academy of Fine Arts in Vienna”), where he was appointed full professor in 1940. From 1934 onwards, Eigenberger was active in the *Nationalsozialistische Deutsche Arbeiterpartei* (NSDAP) in an illegal capacity and officially joined the

- party on 1 May, 1938. He was also a sponsoring member of the SS from 1934 and served as NS-Dozentenführer (“Nazi lecturers’ leader”) at the “Academy of Fine Arts”. Ferihumer, K. and Schober, R. (2019) ‘Eigenberger, Robert’, *Lexikon der österreichischen Provenienzforschung*, Kommission für Provenienzforschung (“Commission for Provenance Research”), available at: <https://www.lexikon-provenienzforschung.org/eigenberger-robert> (Accessed: 5 June, 2025).
- 77 Robert Streibel, *Edith Crossmann [sic!] und der schwarze Prinz* (“Edith Crossmann and the Black Prince”), streibel.at, 25 February, 2024. Available at: <https://streibel.at/edith-crossmann-und-der-schwarze-prinz/> (Accessed: 5 June, 2025).
- 78 The earliest documented involvement of Robert Eigenberger as an expert for the *Dorotheum* dates back to 1930. Nevertheless, prior engagements with the auction house cannot be excluded in light of the present state of the sources. Konstantin Ferihumer, and René Schober (2019), ‘Eigenberger, Robert’, *Lexikon der österreichischen Provenienzforschung*, Kommission für Provenienzforschung (“Commission for Provenance Research”). Available at: <https://www.lexikon-provenienzforschung.org/eigenberger-robert> (Accessed: 5 June, 2025)
- 79 Hugo Werner (Vienna, 24 March, 1882 – Vienna, 24 March, 1911) was managing director of the *Julius Eckstein* company in Vienna. The company was a general merchandise shop (with gold and silverware) and haberdashery (i.e. a bedding, shirt or haberdashery shop) with branches at Kaiserstraße 35 and Lerchenfelder Straße 147 in Vienna.
- 80 Felix Klein, *Historisches Wiener Melderegister* (“Historical Viennese registration archive”), documents in the *Wiener Stadt- und Landesarchiv* (“Municipal and Provincial Archives of Vienna”). Father: Franz Josef Klein (b. 19 March, 1850). Mother: Louise Klein, née Brandl (7 April, 1855–18 September, 1941).
- 81 According to the documents in the *Historisches Wiener Melderegister* (“Historical Viennese registration archive”), Felix Klein was registered at Feldmühlgasse 11 in Vienna between 10 January, 1927 and 13 March, 1938.
- 82 I owe this information to Monika Mayer, provenance researcher from the *Research Center of the Belvedere*, Vienna.
- 83 Information from Joanna Crossman (b. London 1940). Joanna Crossman had an identical twin sister Georgina Felicitas Crossman (London 1940–London 2004). Joanna and Georgina were daughters of Edith and Victor Crossman (Grossman) (Vienna 1896–London 1978) and granddaughters of Ernestine Klein.
- 84 Felix Klein was registered as a member of the board of *Klein & Brandl A.G.* from 22 December, 1923.
- 85 In Budapest, the brothers Otto and Felix Klein ran a wine import and export business at the prominent address Sas utca 1. (*Hungarian Wine Newspaper* [Budapest: 19 June, 1920]). In the building located at the corner of Sas utca and József Attila utca lived, among others, the Hungarian writer Ferenc Ferdinánd Baumgarten (1880–1927).
- 86 Felix Klein was the leading shareholder of the *Dr Megyeri AG* in Kenyérmező (see: Appendix B), a stretch on land in the Hungarian lowlands, which, apart from large estates, owned a winery that he regularly visited with his wife Ernestine. It can be assumed that Felix Klein acquired large parts of the company after the death of the owner, Dr Izidor Krausz Megyeri, and converted it into a public limited company. Megyeri was a prominent Hungarian industrialist and entrepreneur of Jewish origin. Megyeri resided in a magnificent villa at Andrásy út 109 in Budapest, which today houses the *Embassy of the Republic of Korea*.
- 87 *Österreichisches Staatsarchiv*, Vienna (ÖStA, Vienna) (“National Archives of Austria”).
- 88 Although Felix and Otto’s mother Louise fled the day after the Anschluss, she later returned to Vienna with Otto and remained there until he ultimately fled to Hungary to escape Nazi persecution (see below).
- 89 Michael Wladika, “Otto and Julie Klein” in “15. und 16. Bericht des amtsführenden Stadtrates für Kultur und Wissenschaft über die gemäß dem Gemeinderatsbeschluss vom 29. April 1999 in der Fassung vom 29. April 2011 erfolgte Übereignung von Kunst- und Kulturgegenständen aus den Sammlungen der Museen der Stadt Wien, der Wienbibliothek im Rathaus sowie dem Jüdischen Museum der Stadt Wien” (My translation: “15th and 16th Report of the Executive City Councillor for Culture and Science on the transfer of ownership of art and cultural objects from the collections of the *Wien Museum*, the *Vienna City Library* and the *Jewish Museum Vienna*) in accordance with the City Council resolution of 29 April, 1999 as amended on 29 April, 2011 (Vienna: 21 November, 2016), 118-125, 120.
- 90 Message from Joanna Crossman to the author, referring to memories of her mother, Edith Crossman.
- 91 Message from Joanna Crossman to the author.
- 92 Esztergom Kenyérmező is a locality in Komárom–Esztergom County, Central Transdanubia, Hungary.
- 93 A letter from Felix Klein to Fedor Vest reveals that he was in Nice on July 30, 1939.
- 94 ÖStA, Vienna. In Monte Carlo, Ernestine and Felix Klein lived in the Rue Emile de Loth.
- 95 Message from Johanna Crossman to the author.
- 96 M. Wladika 2016, 120.
- 97 M. Wladika 2016, 122.
- 98 M. Wladika 2016, 121.
- 99 Julie Klein’s declaration of assets lists her as the owner of an art collection, which she valued at “circa RM 150,000”. ÖStA. A painting by Francesco Bassano (*Die Beschneidung Christi* [“The Circumcision of Christ”], ca. 210 by 160 cm), which was also missing but not listed in the forced sale, has so far been considered lost. Even though Felix Klein believes that he saw this painting in a Viennese museum [*Belvedere*] after the end of the world war, his searches have been unsuccessful.
- 100 On 3 December, 2002, the following painting was handed over to the heirs of Otto Klein: Moritz Michael Daffinger, *Der Schauspieler Josef Koberwein als Herzog Alfons in Goethes Tasso*, oil on canvas, 56 by 42.5 cm, former inv. no. 4319. I would like to thank Monika Mayer from the *Research Center* at the *Belvedere* in Vienna for providing me with the restitution request from Otto and Julie Klein.
- 101 In 2016, the *Wien Museum* restituted the following watercolour to the heirs of Otto Klein: Johann Christian Schoeller, *Die Local – Posse*, 1840, 22 by 28 cm, former inv. no. 60.560 and acquired it from them on 1 September, 2017. The heiress of the painting from Düsseldorf was Joyce May Klein (7 March, 1926–9 January, 2025), the sister-in-law of Otto and Julie Klein.
- 102 In 2021, the following painting was restituted to the heirs of Otto Klein: Johann Christian Brand, *Small Landscape*, c. 1755, oil on canvas, former inv. no. mkp.M 133.
- 103 Franz (Frank) Josef Klein and his wife Joyce May Klein (AUS), as well as Anna Klein (USA).
- 104 ÖStA, Vienna.
- 105 According to Edith Crossman’s recollection, Felix Klein acquired the sculpture directly from Gustinus Ambrosi. (Robert Streibel). Since Edith Crossman mentions her 16th birthday in connection with the purchase, the acquisition could have taken place around 1924.
- 106 Order of the *Amtsgericht Wien I.* (“District Court of Vienna I”), 115 E 278/39/16 (lot 252, Gustinus Ambrosi, *Bathers*, Carrara).
- 107 Offered as lot no. 247 in the auction in question, this 112 by 165 cm painting with a gold frame depicts a landscape with a flock of sheep.
- 108 Memoirs of Edith Crossman and her daughter Joanna Crossman. Notes to the author. A document from the *Hilfsfonds* (“Relief Fund”) to the *Amt der Wiener Landesregierung* (“Vienna Provincial Government”) (MA 61) dated 3 February, 1966 is accompanied by a letter with personal remarks from Felix Klein, which also mentions art ownership: “Ich war vor dem 13.3.1938 führender Aktionär und Vizepräsident der Klein & Brandl A.G. in Wien XIII. und führender Aktionär der Dr. Magyeri [sic!] rt. in Kenyer Mező [sic!] bei Gran und besass zahlreiche Beteiligungen an Industrie- und Handelsunternehmungen im Auslande, zahlreiche Liegenschaften in Österreich, Bargeld, Bankguthaben, Gold und Silber, Kunstschatze usw.” (My translation: “Before 13 March 1938 I was a leading shareholder and vice-president of *Klein & Brandl A. G.* in Vienna XIII. G. in Vienna XIII. and leading shareholder of *Dr Megyeri rt.* in Kenyérmező near Gran and owned numerous shares in industrial and commercial enterprises abroad, numerous properties in Austria, cash, bank deposits, gold and silver, art treasures, etc.”) Felix Klein went on to state that “after the end of the war [...] he had around 100 restitution proceedings pending, “of which around 40 related to real estate.” (ÖStA, Vienna). However, the letter contains no reference to possible restitution requests for her art collection. To date, no list of her art collection has been found. Since, in contrast to the art collection of his brother Otto and his sister-in-law Julie (see below), none of their artworks could be located in a public collection, it made no sense to initiate proceedings in this regard. My enquiries in this regard at the *Bundesdenkmalamt* were unsuccessful. I would like to thank Lisa Frank from the *Kommission für Provenienzforschung* in Vienna for her research in the restitution materials and in the archives of the *Bundesdenkmalamt*.
- 109 Magdalena Emin (b. 3 May, 1911 in Vienna) was granted Iranian citizenship on the basis of her marriage to the Iranian intestine dealer Nato Emin. After the purchase contract was concluded, which showed Reinhard Werner as the liquidator of Ernestine Klein’s private assets, a political appraisal was obtained from the National Socialist German Workers’ Party (NSDAP), which was issued on 16 June, 1939 and gave Magdalena Emin a very good certificate, meaning that nothing stood in the way of the purchase. (40484/Page 6780 Ref.Winge).
- 110 On 6 May, 1939, the *Österreichische Realitäten A.G.* in Vienna carried out an *Schätzung der Frau Ernestine KLEIN gehörigen Liegenschaft in Wien, XIII, Feldmühlgasse 11 [...]* (My translation: “appraisal of the property belonging to Mrs Ernestine KLEIN in Vienna, XIII, Feldmühlgasse 11 [...]”) and forwarded it to *Klein & Brandl A.G. in Liqu.* which was in liquidation. The valuation was set at RM 76,000, which was just below the purchase price.” (ÖStA, Vienna)
- 111 The files in the ÖStA, Vienna show that Ernestine Klein was also a shareholder in the *Klein & Brandl A.G.* company. However, her name is no longer mentioned in the ongoing proceedings.
- 112 M. Wladika 2016, 121-122.
- 113 ÖStA, Vienna.
- 114 ÖStA, Vienna. In Sanremo, Ernestine and Felix Klein lived in the *Palazzo Monte*

- Grappa at Corso Prazio, Raimondo 53, which no longer exists today.
- 115 The so-called *Klimt Villa* at Feldmühlgasse 11 in Vienna-Hietzing was not originally Gustav Klimt's residence, but from 1911 onward housed his final studio. After 1945, the villa was initially seized by the Soviet occupying forces, later converted into a residence, repeatedly altered, and gradually fell into disrepair. It was not until 2010 that the building was restored as a listed heritage site and, in 2012, opened to the public as a Klimt memorial with a reconstructed studio.
- 116 I am thankful to Lisa Frank of the *Kommission für Provenienzforschung* at the *Bundesministerium für Wohnen, Kunst, Kultur, Medien und Sport* (BMWKMS) ("Federal Ministry of Housing, Art, Culture, Media and Sport") for this information. The archive of the *Bundesdenkmalamt* contained a corresponding export application dated 22 April, 1948 (BDA, file no. 3232/48, [no. 362]).
- 117 See: *Amtsblatt* ("Official Gazette") of the *Wiener Zeitung* (Vienna: 16 July, 1948), 5.
- 118 These four paintings have remained in the family's possession ever since.
- 119 A copy of the will was attached to the *Verlassenschaftssache Ernestine Klein* ("Ernestine Klein probate case") (AZ SA 329/73, Bezirksgericht Innere Stadt, Riemergasse 4). I would like to thank Erika Jakubovits and the *IKG Vienna* ("Jewish Community Vienna") for their valuable support in the search for the documents.
- 120 A copy of the will was attached to the *Verlassenschaftssache Felix Klein* ("Felix Klein probate case") (AZ SA 185/74, BG Innere Stadt, Riemergasse 4). I would like to thank Erika Jakubovits and the *IKG Vienna* ("Jewish Community Vienna") for their valuable support in the search for the documents.
- 121 Zsófia Végvári, "A Fekete Herceg", https://festmenyvizsgalat.blog.hu/2025/03/22/a_fekete_herceg_195 (accessed 19 April, 2025).
- 122 Zsófia Végvári, *Complex Painting Examination, Fekete férfi Portéja* (Budapest: 7 March, 2022). As part of the examination, various imaging and analytical methods were employed, including photography under normal light, UV-induced luminescence photography, and infrared (IR) reflectography. In addition, stereomicroscopic detail photographs were taken. The analysis also comprised an X-ray examination and a X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF). The highly detailed examination report also takes into account two paper labels found on the stretcher: one is circular with a finely serrated edge, located at the upper left corner, with no visible inscription; the other is a partially dissolved rectangular label bearing the printed number [6]846, which may represent a consignment number from the *Dorotheum* auction house in Vienna. Furthermore, the hand-written number 9171 appears on the lower part of the stretcher.
- 123 The name of the person concerned is known to the author but has been anonymized for reasons of privacy protection.
- 124 See note 117.
- 125 See note 117.
- 126 No export application for this painting can be found in the records of the *Bundesdenkmalamt* ("Federal Monuments Office") in Vienna. I am grateful to Lisa Frank (emails dated 1 March, 2024 and 7 April, 2025) and Eva-Maria Gärtner (telephone conversation on 23 May, 2025) for this information. The transfer of the Klimt painting to Hungary in the months following Ernestine Klein's letter of August 1938 occurred at a time when no national register of cultural property existed and there was no legal obligation to report or register privately owned artworks. Cultural affairs fell under the jurisdiction of the *Vallás- és Közoktatásügyi Minisztérium* ("Ministry of Religion and Public Education"), which, however, had no sovereign authority over private art ownership. A systematic inventory or export control mechanism—such as the *Cultural Property Protection Ordinance* already in place in the *German Reich*—had not been implemented in Hungary. Moreover, a general obligation for Jewish citizens to declare assets or foreign currency only came into force with the enactment of the Hungarian "Jewish Laws" beginning in 1939. It was not until the passage of Act No. LXIV/2001 on the Protection of Cultural Heritage that a national register for cultural goods (*kulturális javak országos nyilvántartása*) was established, introducing a mandatory reporting requirement that has since also applied to private individuals.
- 127 Hungarian: *Dr. Megyeri Mezőgazdasági R.T.* ("Dr. Megyeri Agricultural Industrial Company"), see: Appendix B.
- 128 The full nature of Felix and Ernestine Klein's Prague assets and respective legal advisors is currently unknown.
- 129 The address is unconfirmed; the individual may have been a close associate, possibly a sister, of Fedor Vest.
- 130 During technical examinations (see above) of the painting, several minor early damages were identified, including a short cut in the neck area. However, these did not constitute significant or material damage that would substantiate the extent of harm alleged by Fedor Vest or justify his related financial claims.
- 131 On 20 April, 1948, *Wiener Zeitung* listed, among the company registrations recorded by the *Wiener Handelsgericht* ("Vienna Commercial Court"), the company "Erik Klaus-Bülow & Co." (Vienna I, Bösendorferstraße 2, import and export trade in glassware, bijouterie and costume jewelry, textiles, and haberdashery), with Grete Werner of Vienna named as a partner. *Wiener Zeitung*, no. 95 (Vienna: 20 April, 1948), 7. Whether this refers to the individual mentioned in the letter could not be determined to date. It is possible that Grete Werner was a relative of Ernestine Klein's first husband.
- 132 Dr. Ferencz Horn was as a board member of the *Dr. Megyeri AG* as early as 1924. *Nagy Magyar Compass*, 49/2 (Budapest: 1925), 575.
- 133 *Artex* was a Hungarian state-owned foreign trade company established after the Second World War. It was primarily responsible for the export of artworks, antiques, and cultural property, serving as the official export agency through which many paintings and other art objects were transferred to Western countries. (See: Thomas Buomberger, *Raubkunst – Kunstraub. Die Schweiz und der Handel mit gestohlenen Kulturgütern zur Zeit des Nationalsozialismus*. Federal Office of Culture [Bern: 2001]. This publication provides an in-depth discussion of *Artex's* role in the international art trade, particularly in the context of restitution cases and the handling of cultural objects of questionable provenance.)
- 134 The Hungarian address directory *Magyarország kereskedelmi, ipari és mezőgazdasági címtára* (1924, 340) lists the company's headquarters at Veres Pálné utca 17 in Budapest; it was later located at Bálvány utca 22.
- 135 See: Appendix B.
- 136 See the newly established joint-stock company registered in the *Budapester Königliches Handelsregister* ("Royal Commercial Register of Budapest") in 1921, following the death of Dr. Izidor Megyeri (Ref. No. I. 29. Cg 13295/3. 17741/1), published in *Központi Értesítő*, Issue 17, vol. 46 (Budapest: 19 May, 1921), 444–445. Among other matters, the registration records the acquisition of the so-called *Kenyérmező Estate*, which formed part of the estate of Dr. Izidor Megyeri, who died in Budapest on 7 March, 1920, and which is entered in the land registry under entries nos. 248, 2197, and 2209 of Esztergom.
- 137 Fedor Vest died in Budapest, not Klagenfurt (as sometimes incorrectly stated in literature. This information was kindly provided by Noémi Benke (Budapest) on 27 May, 2025).
- 138 Fedor Vest, *Hogyan dolgoznak a bolszevisták? Mik az eszközeik?* ("How Do the Bolsheviks Work?"), (Szeged, Engel Lajos Könyvnyomdája [1919]). In his pamphlet, Vest portrayed the Hungarian rural population as immune to Bolshevik ideology, claiming that the peasants' souls did not provide fertile ground for internationalism.
- 139 András B. Vágvolgyi, "Conti utca" (Conti Street), *Ex Symposion*, no. 103 (2019), 58–60. Accessed at: https://epa.oszk.hu/03700/03787/00003/pdf/EPA03787_ex_symposion_2019_103_058-060.pdf.
- 140 Fedor Vest's sister was Freiin, Noble Margarete Maria Johanna Perčević von Odavna (b. 10 February, 1890 in Timișoara). On 6 June, 1918, she married in Vienna the well-known and controversial Croatian monarchist leader Ivan Arthur Armin Felix Perčević, Edler von Odavna (1881–1947). According to *Adolph Lehmann's Allgemeiner Wohnungs-Anzeiger*, she lived at least until 1936 at Karolinengasse 7, Vienna. Perčević, who remained in Vienna as an exile after the World War I, joined the Vienna exile circle of Field Marshal Svetozar Boroevič von Bojna and later became a high-ranking Ustaša official. After the end of the war, he was sentenced to death by the Supreme Court of the *People's Republic of Croatia* and executed in Zagreb in 1947 (cf. "All Accused Ministers Sentenced to Death," in: *Neue Zeit*, vol. 3, no. 130 [Graz: 10 June, 1947], 2).
- 141 See the article "Baron Vest und sein einflussreicher Schwager" ("Baron Vest and His Influential Brother-in-Law"), in *Der Abend*, no. 115 (Vienna: 19 May, 1932), 2; as well as: *Die Stunde*, vol. 10, no. 2756 (Vienna: 21 May, 1932), 3.
- 142 *Das kleine Volksblatt*, no. 172 (Vienna: 22 June, 1932), 10.
- 143 Courtesy of Zsófia Végvári, 25 May, 2025.
- 144 The reference to Éva Vest's maiden name is owed to Zsófia Végvári.
- 145 The name of the person concerned is known to the author but has been anonymized for reasons of privacy protection.
- 146 See note 145.
- 147 See note 145.
- 148 See note 145.
- 149 See note 38.
- 150 The examination report has been made available to the author.
- 151 This statement is based on the article *Szürke zóna* by Péter Hamvay, published on 15 May, 2025 in the magazine *hvg360*, as well as on a communication from one of my Hungarian sources.
- 152 I intended to have this confirmed by Eleni Korani, yet my inquiries have remained unanswered to this day.
- 153 Péter Molnos (2 April, 2025). *Elvesztettünk egy Klimtet?!* (25 May, 2025). Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fpeter.molnos%2Fposts%2Fpfbid02j7CaEz9de9nd7q9H2Kk9EfNeGSRdnmMDdqAcRZtwyZhvH5NHZNX8tQSSVSnwkaFl&show_text=true&width=500
- 154 Information kindly provided to the author on 24 May, 2025.
- 155 Information kindly provided to the author by *Custodian 4* on 25 May, 2025 (The name of the person concerned is known to the author but has been anonymized

- for reasons of privacy protection).
- 156 Original text quote: “Tájékoztatom, hogy az alábbi, Ön által megadott adatokkal és fényképekkel meghatározott tárgyak Magyarország területéről történő kivitele nem engedélyköteles, a kivitel örökségvédelmi szempontból engedély nélkül jogszerű. [...] Tekintettel arra, hogy az Ön által megadott adatokkal és fényképekkel meghatározott tárgyak nem tartoznak ebbe a körbe, ezért a Kötv. 57. § (1) bekezdése alapján a hatóság engedélye nélkül vihetők ki az országból.”
 - 157 Information kindly provided by *Custodian 4* on 25 May, 2025.
 - 158 I was able to undertake a close study of the painting at *Wienerroither & Kohlbacher* in Vienna. The existence of Zsófia Végvári’s detailed scientific examination report only came to my attention at a considerably later stage.
 - 159 The report was completed on 2 March, 2024. Analytical methods included photography in visible light and short-wave infrared, digital X-ray radiography, ultraviolet and infrared photography, infrared reflectography, and X-ray fluorescence analysis for pigment identification.
 - 160 Péter Hamvay, “Előkerült egy Klimt-festmény – szürke zóna,” *hvg.hu*, 17 May, 2025, https://hvg.hu/360/20250517_hvg-elokerult-klimt-festmeny-szurke-zona; Olga Kronsteiner, Steht Klimts „Afrikanischer Prinz’ unter Schmuggelverdacht?,” *Der Standard*, 21 May, 2025, <https://www.derstandard.at/story/3000000270680/steht-klimts-afrikanischer-prinz-unter-schmuggelverdacht>; Alex Greenberger, “Debate Rages over Whether Rediscovered Klimt Painting Was ‘Smuggled’ out of Hungary,” *ARTnews*, 22 May, 2025. <https://www.artnews.com/art-news/news/rediscovered-klimt-painting-tefaf-maas-tricht-export-debate-1234743209/>.
 - 161 Péter Hamvay, “Lázár: Ha kell a Klimt-kép, tisztességes megegyezéssel kell megvásárolni,” *hvg.hu*, 13 June, 2025, https://hvg.hu/itthon/20250613_lazar-ha-kell-a-klimt-kep-tisztessages-megegyezessel-kell-megvasarolni-ebx.
 - 162 The *Építési és Közlekedési Minisztérium* (“Ministry of Construction and Transport”) is, among other responsibilities, the authority in charge of issuing export licenses concerning the protection of monuments and cultural property. In the article, Minister Lázár commented, among other things, on the legal assessment of the Klimt painting’s export and announced plans for an amendment to the relevant legislation. Furthermore, he declared that a comprehensive internal administrative review would be conducted, aimed at determining whether the competent authorities had acted in accordance with the applicable legal provisions and whether they had exhausted all available means to clarify the facts of the case.
 - 163 See: United States Department of State, *Washington Conference Principles on Nazi-Confiscated Art*, 3 December, 1998, <https://www.state.gov/washington-conference-principles-on-nazi-confiscated-art/>.
 - 164 Péter Hamvay, “Klimt Affair: László Baán Proposes National Art Acquisition Fund of 6 Billion HUF Per Year” (*Klimt-ügy: Nemzeti műtárgyvásárlási alap létrehozását sürgeti Baán László*), *HVG*, June 16, 2025, https://hvg.hu/kultura/20250616_klimt-fekete-herceg-Baan-Laszlo-mutargyvasarlas.
 - 165 See: *Living Culture Foundation Namibia*. *Living Culture Foundation Namibia*. <https://www.lcfn.info> (accessed 7 June, 2025).
 - 166 The *Állatkert* in Budapest, that is, the *Zoological Garden*, was a central site in 1896 as part of the Millennium celebrations marking the thousandth anniversary of the Magyars’ settlement of the Carpathian Basin (Honfoglalás) in the year 896. On the official site map of the Millennium Exhibition, the “African Village” was listed under number 128 (Afrika-kiállítás).
 - 167 See the detailed article: D.G.A., *Egy darab Afrika Budapestén* (“A Piece of Africa in Budapest”), in: *Vasárnapi Ujság*, vol. 43, no. 35 (Budapest: 30 August, 1896), 575–576.
 - 168 The exhibition took place at *Groß-Venedig* (“Velké Benátky”). *Groß-Venedig* was, around 1900, the popular Czech cultural name for the *Vltava island of Štvanice*—also known as the *Hetz-Insel* (“Hetz Island”)—located in the Holešovice district north of Karlsbrücke (“Charles Bridge”) in Prague. See the event advertisement in *Prager Tagblatt* (Prague: 5 September, 1897), 19.
 - 169 The troupe performed in the park of the *Industrial Hall*. See, for example: “Die Aschanti-Neger in Graz,” in *Grazer Tagblatt*, no. 249, vol. 7 (Graz: 8 September, 1897), 4. The first performance took place on 7 September, 1897. Viktor Bamberger accompanied the troupe, which consisted of 40 *Ashanti*, including 15 men, 5 women, 8 girls, and 12 children.
 - 170 The *Jeanette Woermann* was launched in 1893 by *Blohm & Voss* in Hamburg.
 - 171 Moriz Findling, “Von Wien nach Accra,” in *Hamburger Freie Presse*, supplement to no. 1460 (Hamburg: 4 November 1897), [5]. According to the shipping news in the *Hamburger Fremden-Blatt*, “Jeannette Woermann” departed Hamburg on 31 October, 1898 and set sail from Cuxhaven on 1 November at 9 p.m. *Hamburger Fremden-Blatt*, no. 258, vol. 69 (Hamburg: 3 November, 1897), [8].
 - 172 *Neue Freie Presse* (Vienna: 22 October, 1897), 7.
 - 173 Moriz Findling, “Von Wien nach Accra,” in Supplement to no. 1460 of *Hamburger Freie Presse* (Hamburg: 4 November, 1897), [5].
 - 174 R-s-s, “Bland ashantis och javaneser,” in *Smålandsposten*, no. 169 (Wexjö [present-day: Växjö]: 3 November, 1897), 3.
 - 175 “Mörka främlingar i Stockholm,” in: *Norrteje Tidning*, no. 88 (Stockholm: 3 November, 1897), 2.
 - 176 *Hamburger Fremdenblatt* (Hamburg: 30 March, 1898), 18. A girl named “Askio Kai Augusta Berolina,” daughter of “deputy chief Emanuel W. R. Ababio” was baptized.
 - 177 The same applies to the *Ashanti* troupe the following year. A journalist from the *Dresdner Nachrichten* wrote: “Aside from these performances, the attention of the garden’s visitors is now primarily directed toward the Ashanti village, where one has the opportunity to observe various artisans—such as weavers, tailors, carpenters, bronze workers, gold- and silversmiths—at work.” *Dresdner Nachrichten*, no. 200, vol. 44 (Dresden: 21 July, 1899), [9].
 - 178 *Hamburgischer Correspondent*, Morning Edition, no. 407 (Hamburg: 1 September, 1898), 10.
 - 179 *Hamburger Echo* (Hamburg: 21 October, 1898), 2. The steamship *Anna Woermann* was formerly the *Antonina*, acquired in 1897 and renamed *Anna Woermann*. It was scuttled on 9 August, 1914 to block the harbor in Douala (CM), raised and repaired by Britain in 1916, renamed *Polanna*, torpedoed in 1917, and sunk again.
 - 180 “Telegr. Schiffs-Meldungen,” in *Hamburgischer Correspondent*, no. 498, Evening Edition (Hamburg: 24 October, 1898), 15.
 - 181 *Prager Tagblatt*, no. 223 (Prague: 13 August, 1899), 6.
 - 182 “In the autumn of last year [1898], the caravan had returned to its African homeland to reunite with their families. By March of this year [1899], they had already set sail for Europe again [...]” reported the *Dresdner Nachrichten* on 21 July, 1899. *Dresdner Nachrichten*, no. 200, vol. 44 (Dresden: 21 July, 1899), [9].
 - 183 Launched in 1890 by the *Blohm & Voss* shipyard in Hamburg, the *Eduard Bohlen* was, according to the shipyard’s specifications, designed to accommodate 46 passengers. It can be assumed that the Ashanti individuals traveling on board were transported as deck passengers. In 1909, the *Eduard Bohlen* ran aground on the coast of *Deutsch-Südwestafrika* (present-day: Namibia).
 - 184 In the original: “eine größere Truppe Aschanti-Neger” – a phrase reflecting the racially charged and colonialist terminology of the time, which has not been retained in this translation.
 - 185 “Schwarze Besucher,” in *Hamburgischer Correspondent – Abend-Ausgabe*, no. 200 (Hamburg: 29 April, 1899), 4. The *Hamburger Fremdenblatt* also reported on the expected arrival of the approximately 70-member Ashanti troupe intended for the *Wiener Tiergarten* (“Vienna Zoological Garden”), noting that, *dass die Hamburger [...] in der Truppe viele Bekannte aus dem vorigen Jahre antreffen werden* (“the people of Hamburg [...] will recognize many familiar faces from the previous year among the group”). See: „Aschanti-Truppe,” in *Erste Beilage zum Hamburger Fremden-Blatt*, no. 98 (Hamburg: 27 April, 1899).
 - 186 “Das Aschanti-Dorf im Zoologischen Garten,” in *Leipziger Tageblatt und Anzeiger – Frühausgabe* (Leipzig: 3 June, 1899), 9.
 - 187 Dominika Czarnačka and Dagnosław Demski, “Introduction: From Western to Peripheral Voices,” in *Staged Otherness. Ethnic Shows in Central and Eastern Europe 1850–1939* (Budapest: 2021), 33, as cited in Dominika Czarnačka, “A w niedziale szło się oglądać ludzi: Pokazy etnograficzne we wrocławskim ogrodzie zoologicznym 1876–1930” [“And on Sunday We Went to Watch the People’: Ethnographic Shows in the Wrocław Zoological Garden between 1876 and 1930”], in *Etnografia Polska* 62, nos. 1–2 (Warszawa: 2018), 183–98.
 - 188 *Dresdner Nachrichten*, no. 200, vol. 44 (Dresden: 21 July, 1899), [9]. During his stay in Leipzig, Victor Bamberger was accompanied by Mr. Drexler, who acted as his business manager. See: “Westafrika in Leipzig – Das Aschantidorf im Zoologischen Garten,” in *Leipziger Tageblatt und Anzeiger* (Leipzig: 21 May 1899), 13.
 - 189 At the time of the *Ashanti* troupe’s visit in 1899, Königsberg already maintained a zoological garden, established in 1896, which functioned as one of the key venues for ethnographic and zoological spectacles in East Prussia.
 - 190 “Das Aschanti-Dorf,” in *Prager Tagblatt*, no. 223 (Prague: 13 August, 1899), 6.
 - 191 “Die Aschanti im Wiener Thiergarten,” in *Neue Freie Presse*, no. 12580 (Vienna: 31 August, 1899), 7. According to the text, the Ashanti group presented to the Viennese audience includes several recognizable figures as well as a considerable number of new participants.
 - 192 “Die Aschanti in Wien” (“The Ashanti in Vienna”), in *Neues Wiener Journal*, no. 2104 (Vienna: 1 September, 1899), 5.
 - 193 The handbill from September 1899 is reprinted in: Clemens Marschall, “Affentheater im Wurstelprater,” in: *Wiener Zeitung* (Vienna: 21 April, 2016).
 - 194 “Nach Beendigung der Productionen werden die Aschanti von den Wienern mit Liebenswürdigkeiten überschüttet. Männer, Weiber, Mädchen und Knaben werden zum Nachtmahl geladen, und es gewährt einen eigenthümlichen Anblick, an der Mehrzahl der Tische mitten unter den Wienern Aschanti in lebhafter Unterhaltung sitzen zu sehen.” (My translation: “After the conclusion of

- the performances, the Ashanti are showered with kindnesses by the Viennese. Men, women, girls, and boys are invited to supper, and it presents a peculiar sight to see Ashanti seated in lively conversation among the Viennese at most of the tables.” “Die Aschanti in Wien” (“The Ashanti in Vienna”), in *Neues Wiener Journal*, no. 2104 (Vienna: 1 September, 1899), 5.
- 195 See: *Hamburgischer Correspondent*, Evening Edition, no. 412, vol. 169 (Hamburg: 2 September, 1899), 11–12.
- 196 “Wild-Südafrika” (*Wild South Africa*) was advertised as a grand “military-realist spectacle in 4 divisions and 60 scenes.” The so-called “divisions” illustrated the scenes *South African Landscape, In the Homeland of the Boers, The Matabele Uprising, and The Battle of Spion Kop*. *Illustriertes Wiener Extrablatt*, no. 147 (Vienna: 31 May, 1901), 15). Among the other prominent impresarios active during this period were William Frederick Cody (better known as Buffalo Bill), Robert A. Cunningham, Eduard Gehring, Ferdinand Gravier (cf. above), Carl and Fritz Marquardt, Heinrich and Willy Möller, Emanuel Porfi, Jean-Alfred Vigé, and John Wood, also referred to as Hood.
- 197 “Wild-Süd-Afrika” (*Wild South Africa*), in *Wiener Allgemeine Zeitung*, no. 6978 (Vienna: 16 June 1901), 6. The term *Bafutos* refers to members of the Bafut people, an ethnic group located in the northwest of present-day Cameroon.
- 198 “Wild-Südafrika im Uraniagarten” (“Wild South Africa in the Urania Garden”), in *Deutsches Tagblatt – Ostdeutsche Rundschau, Morgenblatt*, no. 142 (Vienna: May 25, 1901), 6.
- 199 “Die Buren kommen wieder” (“The Boers Are Returning”), in *Deutsches Tagblatt – Ostdeutsche Rundschau*, Morning Edition, no. 224 (Vienna: 17 August, 1901), 5.
- 200 The financial management of the exhibition, which lasted approximately three months in the *Urania Park* in the *Prater*, was evidently handled through the company *The Ethnographical Show Co.*, founded by Victor Bamberger. According to reports, Bamberger profited handsomely from the venture, but apparently failed to pay all fees owed to William Caspar, a situation that had particularly adverse effects on the performers. See: “Eine Burenaffaire in Wien”, in *Neues Wiener Journal*, no. 2840 (Vienna: 21 September, 1901), 4.
- 201 See: Yahya Birt, *A Somali Village in Colonial Bradford – An Introduction, Somali Village*, last modified February 20, 2025, <https://somalivillage.org.uk/a-somali-village-in-colonial-bradford-an-introduction/> (accessed June 7, 2025).
- 202 Victor Bamberger was married to Henriette van Dijk (b. 1875 in Amsterdam).
- 203 See: Yahya Birt, see above.
- 204 *Illustrierte Zeitung*, no. 2823 (Leipzig: 5 September, 1897), 189–193 (ill.).
- 205 The drawing held in the *Wien Museum* (inv. 55804/7) is listed in the *Online Sammlung* (“Online Collection”) under the title *Bazar im Aschanti-Dorf* (“Bazaar in the Ashanti Village”), although the original caption published in the *Illustrierte* [sic] *Woche* reads *Ansicht des Dorfes mit den Verkaufsbuden* (“View of the village with the vendor stalls”). The term “bazaar” is inappropriate in this context and exemplifies how museums still often fail to approach the naming and framing of colonial-era depictions with sufficient cultural and historical sensitivity.
- 206 Sadiya Qureshi, *Peoples on Parade: Exhibitions, Empire, and Anthropology in Nineteenth-Century Britain* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2011), 5.
- 207 Zoologischer Garten, Hamburg (“Zoological Garden, Hamburg”), Ashanti Village. 90 Natives from the Gold Coast of West Africa, *Hamburger Fremdenblatt* (Hamburg: 11 September, 1898), 16.
- 208 See the reestablishment of the joint-stock company registered in the *Königliches Handelsregister* (“Royal Commercial Register”) of Budapest in 1921 following the death of Dr. Izidor Megyery (Ref. No. I. 29. Cg 13295/3. 17741/1), in: *Központi Értésítő*, Issue 17, vol. 46 (Budapest: May 19, 1921), 444–445. Among other details, the entry records the acquisition of the so-called *Kenyérmező Estate Enterprise*, which “forms part of the estate of Dr. Izidor Megyery, who died on March 7, 1920, in Budapest, and is registered in the land registry entries nos. 248, 2197, and 2209 of Esztergom; [...]”. According to a contemporary report: “Following the death of the landowner, the *Kenyérmező* estate passed into the leasehold of a joint-stock company.” *Esztergom és Vidéke* (Esztergom: 28 November, 1920), 3.
- 209 megyeri [sic!] Dr. Megyery (Krausz) Izidor János (Pest, 4 September, 1854, Pest – Budapest, 7 March, 1920) was married to Renée Wahrmann (b. 1862), and in a second marriage to Hedvig Wolfner von Újpest (née Brüll, 1875–1964). In the early 1900s, with the permission of the monarch, he replaced his family name *Krausz* with *Megyery* and henceforth bore the name *megyeryi Dr. Megyery Izidor*.
- 210 *Esztergom és Vidéke* (Esztergom: 10 July, 1887) [3].
- 211 *Esztergom és Vidéke* (Esztergom: 10 July, 1887) [3].
- 212 MNL Komárom–Esztergom Vármegyei Levéltára, Esztergom.
- 213 See the Hungarian company directory *Kompasz GPT*, vol. 1926–1927, Budapest, 831. I am indebted to Noémi Benke from Budapest for this reference.
- 214 ÖStA, Vienna.
- 215 ÖStA, Vienna.
- 216 Minutes of the general meeting of the joint-stock company dated October 14, 1940, *Ungarisches Handelsregister* (“Hungarian Commercial Register”).
- 217 *Magyarország kereskedelmi, ipari és mezőgazdasági címtára 1924* (340).
- 218 *Esztergom és Vidéke* (Esztergom: 30 April, 1939, and 6 August, 1939 [3]).
- 219 *Esztergom és Vidéke* (Esztergom: 28 May, 1941), 2.